

Interreg Project
BIGWOOD

REPORT
on
Defined quality requirements

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1. Building standards and quality requirements in Italy and Austria – Noise protection and acoustic regulations

Standards and guidelines:

Austria:

- OIB-5 Guidelines
- Tiroler Bauordnung 2001 (LGBl. Nr. 94/2001 i.d.F. LGBl. Nr. 187/2014)
- Techn. Bauvorschriften 2008 (Landesgesetzblatt Nr. 93/2007 i.d.F. LGBl. Nr. 78/2013)
- ÖNORM B 8115, 1-7

Italy:

- DPCM 05.12.97
- UNI 11367: Acoustic classification of buildings

EN/ISO reference standards:

- ISO 10140 (Laboratory measurement of sound insulation of building elements; part 2: airborne sound measurements)
- ISO 140 – 7 (impact sound measurements); The transmission paths of the edges are included in the measurement
- ISO 717 (Rating of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements; part 1: airborne sound insulation, part 2: impact sound insulation)
- EN 16283 - Field measurement of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements

Terms and units:

- R Sound reduction index (measurement acc. ISO 10140-2)

$$R = 10 \cdot \lg \frac{W_1}{W_2}$$

W_1 Sound power striking the component in W in [W]

W_2 Sound power radiated by the component in W in [W]

Further (assuming that the sound transmittance takes places by only one single separating component):

$$R = D + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{S}{A} \quad \text{with } D = L_1 - L_2$$

L_1 Mean sound pressure level in the sending room in [dB]; ISO 10140

L_2 Mean sound pressure level in the receiving room in [dB]; ISO 10140

S Surface of separating component in [m²]

A Equivalent sound absorption area of the receiving room in [m²]

- R_w Single-number rating sound reduction index (acc. ISO 717-1)
 R_w is used to evaluate separating components used in a bypass-free test bench (single opaque components) and to identify the sound insulation of doors.

- R' Apparent sound reduction index (measurement acc. EN 16283-1)

$$R' = 10 \cdot \lg \frac{W_1}{W_2 + W_3}$$

W_1 Sound power striking the component in [W]

$W_2 + W_3$ Sound power transmitted into the receiving room incl. flanking transmission [W]
in Austrian ÖNORM B 8115-1: W_{tot}

It is evaluated using the formula:

$$R' = D + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{S}{A} \quad \text{with } D = L_1 - L_2$$

L_1 Mean sound pressure level in the sending room in [dB];

L_2 Mean sound pressure level in the receiving room in [dB];

S Surface of separating component in [m²]

A Equivalent sound absorption area of the receiving room in [m²]

The building sound reduction index is specified in ÖNORM B 8115 only for exterior components. In addition to the sound transmission through the external component also the effect of sound transmission by the flanking components is contained.

- R'_w Single number rating apparent sound reduction index (acc. ISO 717)

The single value specification R'_w is determined in the same way as R_w .

- C_{tr} Value that is added to the single number R_w , R'_w or $D_{nT,w}$ in order to consider a specific sound level spectrum

- D_{nT} Standardized sound level difference (acc. EN1283-1)

$$D_{nT} = D + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T}{T_0} \quad \text{with } D = L_1 - L_2$$

D Sound level difference within a building in [dB]

T Reverberation time in [s]

T_0 Reference value for the reverberation time in the receiving room in [s]

- D_n Normalized sound level difference

$$D_n = D + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A_0}{A} \quad \text{with } D = L_1 - L_2$$

- D Sound level difference within a building in [dB]
- A_0 Reference value for the equivalent sound absorption area in [m²]; $A_0 = 10\text{m}^2$
- A Equivalent sound absorption area in the receiving room in [m²]

The single value specification $D_{nT,w}$ (assessed standardized sound level difference) and $D_{n,w}$ (assessed normalized sound level difference) are determined from the values D_{nT} and D_n acc. to ISO 717-1 in the same way as R_w .

- L'_{nT} Standardized impact sound level (acc. EN 16283-2)

$$L'_{nT} = L - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T}{T_0}$$

- L Impact Sound in [dB]
- T Reverberation time in [s]
- T_0 Reference value for the reverberation time in the receiving room in [s]

For living rooms and rooms of similar use and size, the reference value of the reverberation time is $T_0=0,5\text{s}$.

- L'_n Normalized impact sound level (EN 16383-2)

Impact sound level, based on the normalized sound absorption area of $A_0 = 10\text{m}^2$ in the receiving room, considering the sound absorption area A available in the room

$$L'_n = L + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A}{A_0}$$

- L Sound level difference in [dB]
- A Equivalent sound absorption area in the receiving room in [m²]
- A_0 Reference value for the equivalent sound absorption area in [m²]; $A_0 = 10\text{m}^2$

The single value specification $L'_{nT,w}$ (assessed standardized impact sound level) and $L'_{n,w}$ (assessed normalized impact sound level) are determined from the values L'_{nT} and L'_n acc. to ISO 717-2 in the same way as R_w .

Descriptors specified in Austrian standards only:

- R_{res} Resulting sound reduction index (acc. ÖNORM B 8115-1) – *ONLY IN AUSTRIA!*

$$R_{res} = -10 \cdot \lg \frac{1}{\sum S_i} \cdot \sum (S_i \cdot 10^{-\frac{R_i}{10}})$$

R_{res} Resulting sound reduction index in [dB]
 R_i Sound reduction index of the partial area in [dB]
 S_i Surface of the partial area in [m²]

Sound reduction index that is specified for a component that consists of several partial areas with different dimensions and different sound insulation dimensions

- $R_{res,w}$ Assessed resulting building sound reduction index

The single value specification $R'_{res,w}$ is determined in the same way as R_w .

- R'_{res} Resulting building sound reduction index

Building sound reduction index that is specified for a component that consists of several partial areas with different dimensions and different sound insulation dimensions

In addition to the sound transmission through the external component also the effect of sound transmission by the flanking components is contained.

- $R'_{res,w}$ Assessed resulting building sound reduction index

The single value specification $R'_{res,w}$ is determined in the same way as R_w .

Transformations (in dB):

a) Correlation between D_{nT} and D_n

with

$$D_{nT} = D + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T}{T_0} = D - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T_0}{T}$$

$$D_n = D + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A_0}{A} \rightarrow D = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A_0}{A}$$

With (2) in (1)

$$D_{nT} = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A_0}{A} - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T_0}{T}$$

with $A_0 = 10 \text{ m}^3$ and $T_0 = 0,5 \text{ s}$

$$D_{nT} = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{10}{A} - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{0,5}{T} = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{10 \cdot T}{0,16 \cdot V} - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{0,5}{T}$$

$$\text{with } A = 0,16 \cdot \frac{V}{T}$$

$$D_{nT} = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{0,5 \cdot 10 \cdot T}{0,16 \cdot T \cdot V} = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg 31,2 + 10 \cdot \lg V$$

$$D_{nT} = D_n + 10 \cdot \lg V - 14,9$$

Further: with (2) in (1)

$$D_{nT} = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A_0}{A} - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T_0}{T} = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A_0 \cdot T_0}{A \cdot T}$$

with $A \cdot T = 0,16 \cdot V$ and $A_0 \cdot T_0 = 0,16 \cdot V_0$

$$D_{nT} = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{V_0}{V}$$

b) Correlation between L'_{nT} and L'_n

with

$$L'_{nT} = L - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T}{T_0} = L + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T_0}{T}$$

$$L'_n = L + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A}{A_0} \rightarrow L = L'_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A}{A_0}$$

With (7) in (6)

$$L'_{nT} = L'_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A}{A_0} - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T}{T_0}$$

with $A_0 = 10 \text{ m}^3$ and $T_0 = 0,5 \text{ s}$

$$L'_{nT} = L'_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A}{10} - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T}{0,5} = L'_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{0,16 \cdot V}{10 \cdot T} - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{T}{0,5}$$

with $A = 0,16 \cdot \frac{V}{T}$

$$L'_{nT} = L'_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{0,16 \cdot T \cdot V}{0,5 \cdot 10 \cdot T} = L'_n + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{0,5 \cdot 10}{0,16} - 10 \cdot \lg V$$

$$L'_{nT} = L'_n - 10 \cdot \lg V + 14,9$$

c) Correlation between R respectively R' and D_n

with

$$R' = D + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{S}{A}$$

$$D_n = D + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A_0}{A} \rightarrow D = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A_0}{A}$$

With (11) in (10)

$$R' = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A_0}{A} + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{S}{A}$$

$$R' = D_n + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A}{A_0} + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{S}{A} = D_n + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A \cdot S}{A_0 \cdot A}$$

$$R' = D_n + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{S}{A_0} \quad \text{with } A_0 = 10 \text{ m}^3$$

Further:

$$R' = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg \frac{A_0}{A} + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{S}{A}$$

$$R' = D_n + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{S}{A_0}$$

$$\text{with } A_0 = 10 \text{ m}^3 \text{ and } T_0 = 0,5 \text{ s}, A_0 = 0,16 \cdot \frac{V}{T_0}$$

$$R' = D_n + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{S}{0,16 \cdot \frac{V}{T_0}} = D_n + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{1}{V} + 10 \cdot \lg S + 10 \cdot \lg \frac{0,5}{0,16}$$

$$R' = D_n - 10 \cdot \lg V + 10 \cdot \lg S + 4,9$$

Comparison of impact sound and sound level difference standards:

The airborne and impact sound requirements according to DIN 4109 (Germany), ÖNORM B8115-2 (Austria), SIA 181 (Switzerland) and DPCM 5.12.1997 (Italy) are sometimes different, as the following list shows. This means that for example a sound-technically suitable component in Germany does not meet the requirements in Austria. The minimum requirements listed apply to multi-storey residential buildings (measurements including flanking transmittance):

Austria (ÖNORM)	Standard impact sound level	$L'_{nT,w} =$	48dB
	Standard sound level difference	$D_{nT,w} =$	55dB
Germany (DIN)	Standardized impact sound insulation	$L'_{n,w} =$	53dB
	Sound reduction index	$R'_w =$	53 or 54dB
Switzerland (SIA)	Standard impact sound level	$L'_{nT,w} + C_1 =$	53dB
	Standard sound level difference	$D_{nT,w} + C =$	52dB
Italy (DPCM)	Standardized impact sound insulation	$L'_{n,w} =$	63dB
	Sound reduction index	$R'_w =$	50dB

Status June 2013 ⁽¹⁾				Status June 2013 ⁽¹⁾			
Country ⁽²⁾	Descriptor ⁽³⁾	Req. [dB]	Req. [dB]	Country ⁽²⁾	Descriptor ⁽³⁾	Req. [dB]	Req. [dB]
Austria	D_{stc}	≥ 55	≥ 60	Austria	L'_{stc}	≤ 48	≤ 43
Belgium	D_{stc}	≥ 54	≥ 58	Belgium	L'_{stc}	≤ 58 (3)	≤ 50
Bulgaria	R'_w	≥ 53	≥ 53	Bulgaria	L'_{stc}	≤ 53	≤ 53
Croatia	R'_w	≥ 52	≥ 52	Croatia	$L'_{stc}(5)$	≤ 68	≤ 68
Cyprus (8)	N/A	N/A	N/A	Cyprus (9)	N/A	N/A	N/A
Czech Rep.	R'_w	≥ 53	≥ 57	Czech Rep.	L'_{stc}	≤ 55	≤ 48
Denmark	R'_w	≥ 55	≥ 55	Denmark	L'_{stc}	≤ 53	≤ 53
England & Wales	$D_{stc} + C_2$	≥ 45	≥ 45	England & Wales	L'_{stc}	≤ 62	None
Estonia	R'_w	≥ 55	≥ 55	Estonia	L'_{stc}	≤ 53	≤ 53
Finland	R'_w	≥ 55	≥ 55	Finland	$L'_{stc}(4)$	≤ 53 (4)	≤ 53 (4)
France	$D_{stc} + C$	≥ 53	≥ 53	France	L'_{stc}	≤ 58	≤ 58
Germany	R'_w	≥ 53 (4)	≥ 57	Germany	L'_{stc}	≤ 53	≤ 48
Greece (9)	R'_w	≥ (50)	≥ (50)	Greece (10)	L'_{stc}	≤ (60)	≤ (60) 60 info
Hungary	$R'_w + C$	≥ 51	≥ 56	Hungary	L'_{stc}	≤ 55	≤ 45
Iceland	R'_w	≥ 55	≥ 55	Iceland	L'_{stc}	≤ 53	≤ 53
Ireland	D_{stc}	≥ 53 (4)	≥ 53	Ireland	L'_{stc}	≤ 62	None
Italy	R'_w	≥ 50	≥ 50	Italy	L'_{stc}	≤ 63	≤ 63
Latvia	R'_w	≥ 54	≥ 54	Latvia	L'_{stc}	≤ 54	≤ 54
Lithuania	D_{stc} or R'_w	≥ 55	≥ 55	Lithuania	L'_{stc}	≤ 53	≤ 53
Luxembourg (8)	N/A	N/A	N/A	Luxembourg (9)	N/A	N/A	N/A
Macedonia FYR (8)	N/A	N/A	N/A	Macedonia FYR (9)	N/A	N/A	N/A
Malta (8)	N/A	N/A	N/A	Malta (9)	N/A	N/A	N/A
Netherlands	$R'_w + C$	≥ 52	≥ 52	Netherlands	$L'_{stc} + C_1$	≤ 54	≤ 54
Norway	$R'_w(3)$	≥ 55 (3)	≥ 55 (3)	Norway	$L'_{stc}(4)$	≤ 53 (4)	≤ 53 (4)
Poland	$R'_w + C$	≥ 50 (4)	≥ 52 (5)	Poland	L'_{stc}	≤ 58	≤ 53
Portugal	D_{stc}	≥ 50	≥ 50	Portugal	L'_{stc}	≤ 60	≤ 60
Romania (6)	R'_w	≥ 51	≥ 51	Romania (7)	L'_{stc}	≤ 59	≤ 59
Scotland	D_{stc}	≥ 56	≥ 56	Scotland	L'_{stc}	≤ 56	None
Serbia	R'_w	≥ 52	≥ 52	Serbia	L'_{stc}	≤ 68	≤ 68
Slovakia	R'_w or D_{stc}	≥ 53	≥ 57	Slovakia	L'_{stc} or L'_{stc}	≤ 55	≤ 48
Slovenia	R'_w	≥ 52	≥ 52	Slovenia	L'_{stc}	≤ 58	≤ 58
Spain	$D_{stc} = D_{stc} + C$	≥ 50	≥ 50	Spain	L'_{stc}	≤ 65	≤ 65
Sweden	$R'_w + C_{10,210}$	≥ 53	≥ 53	Sweden	$L'_{stc} + C_{10,210}$	≤ 56 (6)	≤ 56 (6)
Switzerland	$D_{stc} + C$	≥ 52 (7)	≥ 55	Switzerland	$L'_{stc} + C_1$	≤ 53 (8)	≤ 50
Turkey (8)	N/A	N/A	N/A	Turkey (9)	N/A	N/A	N/A

Figure 1: Acoustic performance requirements across Europe. Cost Action TU0902, 2013.

SOUND INSULATION REQUIREMENTS IN AUSTRIA

According to the Austrian OIB-5 Guidelines (12 pages) and the ÖNORM B 8115, part 1-7 the following noise protection requirements must be adhered:

- **Structural noise protection:**

- **Requirements for the sound insulation of external components**

The relevant site-related and, if applicable, component-related external noise level is to be determined according to the state of the art using adjustment values L_z (assessment level L_r). This must be done separately for day (6:00 a.m. to 10:00 p.m.) and night, with the less favorable value being used to determine the requirements.

Insofar as no higher requirements result from subsequent tables 1.2.1.A and 1.2.1.B, the values for the assessed resulting building sound reduction index $R'_{res,w}$ of the external components with a total of 33 dB and the assessed sound reduction index R_w of the opaque exterior components must not fall below 43 dB.

For residential buildings, homes, hotels, schools, kindergartens, hospitals, spa buildings, etc., the sound insulation of the exterior components of common rooms must not fall below the following values:

Table 1: Minimum required sound insulation of external components

Minimum required sound insulation of external components for residential buildings, homes, hotels, schools, kindergartens, hospitals, health resorts, etc.								
Significant external noise level [dB]		Total external components [dB]	Opaque external components [dB]	Windows and doors [dB]		Ceilings and walls against unfinished attic spaces [dB]	Ceilings and walls against passageways and garages [dB]	Building partition walls at neighboring property or building site boundaries (each wall) [dB]
Day	Night	$R'_{res,w}$	R_w	R_w	$R_w + C_{tr}$	R'_w	R_w	R_w
≤ 45	≤ 35	33	43	28	23	42	60	48
46-50	36-40	33	43	28	23	42	60	48
51-60	41-50	38	43	33	28	42	60	48
61	51	38,5	43,5	33,5	28,5	47	60	48
62	52	39	44	34	29	47	60	48
63	53	39,5	44,5	34,5	29,5	47	60	48
64	54	40	45	35	30	47	60	48
65	55	40,5	45,5	35,5	30,5	47	60	48
66	56	41	46	36	31	47	60	48
67	57	41,5	46,5	36,5	31,5	47	60	48
68	58	42	47	37	32	47	60	48
69	59	42,5	47,5	37,5	32,5	47	60	48

70	60	43	48	38	33	47	60	48
71	61	44	49	39	34	47	60	48
72	62	45	50	40	35	47	60	48
73	63	46	51	41	36	47	60	48
74	64	47	52	42	37	47	60	48
75	65	48	53	43	38	47	60	48
76	66	49	54	44	39	47	60	48
77	67	50	55	45	40	47	60	48
78	68	51	56	46	41	47	60	48
79	69	52	57	47	42	47	60	48
≥ 80	≥ 70	53	58	48	43	47	60	48

For administration and office buildings and the like, the sound insulation of the exterior components of common rooms must not fall below the following values:

Table 2: Minimum required sound insulation of external components – office buildings

Minimum required sound insulation of external components for administration and office building, etc.								
Significant external noise level [dB]		Total external components [dB]	Opaque external components [dB]	Windows and doors [dB]		Ceilings and walls against unfinished attic spaces [dB]	Ceilings and walls against passageways and garages [dB]	Building partition walls at neighboring property or building site boundaries (each wall) [dB]
Day	Night	$R'_{res,w}$	R_w	R_w	$R_w + C_{tr}$	R'_w	R_w	R_w
≤ 45	≤ 35	33	43	28	23	42	60	48
46-60	36-50	33	43	28	23	42	60	48
61	51	33,5	43	28,5	23,5	42	60	48
62	52	34	43	29	24	42	60	48
63	53	34,5	43	29,5	24,5	42	60	48
64	54	35	43	30	25	42	60	48
65	55	35,5	43	30,5	25,5	42	60	48
66	56	36	43	31	26	42	60	48
67	57	36,5	43	31,5	26,5	42	60	48
68	58	37	43	32	27	42	60	48
69	59	37,5	43	32,5	27,5	42	60	48
70	60	38	43	33	28	42	60	48
71	61	39	44	34	29	42	60	48
72	62	40	45	35	30	42	60	48
73	63	41	46	36	31	42	60	48

Attention: ÖNORM B 8115-2
Part. Walls: $R'_w \geq 52$ dB

74	64	42	47	37	32	42	60	48
75	65	43	48	38	33	42	60	48
76	66	44	49	39	34	42	60	48
77	67	45	50	40	35	42	60	48
78	68	46	51	41	36	42	60	48
79	69	47	52	42	37	42	60	48
≥ 80	≥ 70	48	53	43	38	42	60	48

The sound insulation of any ventilation ducts such as window ventilators or individual room ventilation devices must be as good as that the required assessed resulting building sound reduction index $R'_{res,w}$ of the external components remains fully met when closed. In an open state it may not fall below by more than 5dB.

- Requirements for airborne sound insulation within buildings

Walls, ceilings and fixtures between rooms are to be dimensioned in such a way that the following values of the assessed standard sound level difference $D_{nT,w}$ do not fall below the following values due to the sound transmission through the separating component and the longitudinal sound line, e.g. the flanking components:

Table 3: Minimum required assessed standard sound level difference

Minimum required assessed standard sound level difference $D_{nT,w}$ in buildings		
of	to	$D_{nT,w}$ [dB] without / with connection through doors, windows or other apertures
1 Common rooms	Common rooms of other usage units	55 / 50
	Generally accessible areas (e.g. staircases, corridors, basement rooms, common rooms)	55 / 50
	Adjoining rooms of other usage units	55 / 50
2 Hotel-, class-, hospital rooms, groue rooms in kindergartens and living rooms in homes	Rooms of the equal category	55 / 50
	Generally accessible areas (e.g. staircases, corridors, basement rooms, common rooms)	55 / 38
	Adjoining rooms	55 / 35
3 Adjoining rooms	Common rooms of other usage units	55 / 35
	Generally accessible areas (e.g. staircases, corridors, basement rooms, common rooms)	55 / 35
	Adjoining rooms of other usage units	55 / 35

If no organizational measures are applied, the other usage units are defined as in schools the individual classrooms, in kindergartens the individual group rooms, in hospitals the individual sick rooms, in nursing homes the individual home rooms, in hotels the individual hotel rooms, in administration and office buildings, however, the operational unit used by others..

In the case of buildings with mixed use, the requirements must be applied in accordance with the specific room uses.

Further: Acc. to ÖNORM B 8115-2 the airborne sound level between common or adjoining rooms and adjoining buildings or rooms of adjoining usage units in terraced homes without connections must not fall below $D_{nT,w} = 60$ dB.

- Requirements for airborne sound insulation of doors inside buildings

Unless a higher assessed sound reduction index is required to meet the standard for the respectively assessed standard sound level difference $D_{nT,w}$ according to 1.2.1.C the assessed sound reduction index R_w of doors (door leaf and frame) must not fall below the following values:

Table 4: Minimum required assessed sound reduction index of doors

Minimum required assessed sound reduction index R_w of doors (door leaf and frame)			
	between	and	R_w [dB]
1	Generally accessible areas (e.g. stairwells, corridors)	Common rooms in apartments without acoustically closed vestibules or hallways	42
		Common rooms in apartments with acoustically closed vestibules or hallways	33
2	Common rooms	Common rooms of other usage units	42
		Adjoining rooms of other usage units	33
2	Hotel and hospital rooms, living rooms in homes	Rooms of the equal category	42
		Generally accessible areas (e.g. staircases, corridors)	33
3	Classrooms, group rooms in kindergartens	Rooms of the equal category	42
		Generally accessible areas (e.g. staircases, corridors)	28
<p><i>If no organizational measures are applied, the other usage units are defined as in schools the individual classrooms, in kindergartens the individual group rooms, in hospitals the individual sick rooms, in nursing homes the individual home rooms, in hotels the individual hotel rooms, in administration and office buildings, however, the operational unit used by others..</i></p> <p><i>In the case of buildings with mixed use, the requirements must be applied in accordance with the specific room uses.</i></p>			

- **Requirements for impact sound insulation in buildings**

The assessed standard impact sound level $L'_{nT,w}$ in rooms must not exceed the following values:

Table 5: Maximum permissible assessed standard impact sound level

Maximum permissible assessed standard impact sound level $L'_{nT,w}$			
	of	to	$L'_{nT,w}$ [dB]
1	Common rooms	Rooms for other usage units (apartments, schools, kindergartens, hospitals, hotels, homes, administration and office buildings and comparable uses)	48
		Generally accessible terraces, roof gardens, balconies, loggias and attics	48
		Generally accessible areas (e.g. stairwells, arcades)	50
		Usable terraces, roof gardens, loggias and attics	53
		Balconies	55
2	Adjoining rooms	Rooms for other usage units (apartments, schools, kindergartens, hospitals, hotels, homes, administration and office buildings and comparable uses)	53
		Generally accessible terraces, roof gardens, balconies, loggias and attics	53
		Generally accessible areas (e.g. stairwells, arcades)	55
		Usable terraces, roof gardens, loggias and attics	58
		Balconies	60
<i>If no organizational measures are applied, the other usage units are defined as in schools the individual classrooms, in kindergartens the individual group rooms, in hospitals the individual sick rooms, in nursing homes the individual home rooms, in hotels the individual hotel rooms, in administration and office buildings, however, the operational unit used by others..</i>			
<i>In the case of buildings with mixed use, the requirements must be applied in accordance with the specific room uses.</i>			

Further: acc. to ÖNORM B 8115-2 the impact sound level between common rooms and adjoining buildings or adjoining usage units in terraced homes must not exceed $L'_{nT,w} = 43$ dB. Stricter requirements also occur in buildings with operating facilities (depending on the activity and the day or night time).

The requirements are to be met without considering a floor covering that can be assigned to the furnishings (e.g. carpets, mats); Pavements that are permanently applied (e.g. screeds, adhesive parquet, tiled flooring) can be considered. For accommodation facilities and for balconies that are not generally accessible, it is permissible to meet the requirements by permanently existing, sound-absorbing footprints (e.g. fitted carpet, glued-on textile coverings, synthetic floors, linoleum).

- **Acoustic requirements for building services systems**

The maximum system noise level $L_{AFmax,nT}$ resulting from the operation of building services systems from other usage units must not exceed 25 dB for constant and intermittent noises and 30 dB for brief noises. Values higher by 5 dB are permitted for side rooms.

If a mechanical ventilation system is available in the own usage unit, for common rooms with the protection aim of sleep (e.g. common rooms in apartments, excluding kitchens), the noises from this system, based on the operating mode that is the minimum required in terms of air hygiene, may not exceed an equivalent system noise level $L_{Aeq,nT}$ of 25 dB, for common rooms with the protection aim of concentration (e.g. classrooms) of 30 dB.

- **Acoustic requirements between terraced houses and adjacent buildings**

Walls between terraced houses or between adjoining terraced house units as well as between adjoining buildings must be designed so that the assessed standard sound level difference $D_{nT,w}$ of 60 dB is not fallen below. Terraced houses in the acoustic sense also include buildings with two instead of three usage units. A value lowered by 5 dB is permitted for side rooms.

The assessed standard impact sound level $L'_{nT,w}$ from adjoining buildings or adjoining terraced house units to rooms in terraced houses and between adjoining buildings must not exceed the value of 43 dB. Terraced houses in the acoustic sense also include buildings with two instead of three usage units. A value 5 dB higher is permitted for side rooms.

- **Additional acoustic requirements for buildings with other than residential, office or school-like uses**

The applicable planning base level L_{PB} in the common room to be protected must not be exceeded by the assessment level L_r . Characteristic peak levels $L_{A,Sp}$ must not exceed the applicable planning base level L_{PB} by more than 10 dB.

The assessed standard impact sound level $L'_{nT,w}$ for common rooms must not exceed the following values:

- 38 dB with usage-related noise development only between 6:00 a.m. and 10:00 p.m.,
- 33 dB with usage-related noise development also between 10:00 p.m. and 6:00 a.m. and
- 60 dB between common rooms of different usage units in salesrooms and in buildings of similar use.

- **Buildings and rooms with specific uses**

For buildings and rooms with specific uses, different requirements may be necessary or sufficient in individual cases. Additional acoustic and organizational measures for the protection against noise can also be considered (e.g. in schools, kindergartens, homes, old people's homes, or buildings with comparable use, nursing homes and hospitals or shelters in extreme locations).

- **Rooms with a very small volume**

For rooms with a volume of no more than 10 m³, the requirements are 5 dB lower.

- **Room acoustics**

- **Audibility requirements**

For rooms with that are used for language purposes (lecture halls, lecture rooms) with a volume V between 30 m^3 and $10,000 \text{ m}^3$, the reverberation time requirement is determined by $T = (0.37 \times \lg V) - 0.14$ in seconds for the octave bands from 250 Hz to 2,000 Hz.

For rooms that are used for communication purposes (classrooms, media rooms, meeting rooms, rooms for audiovisual presentation) with a volume V between 30 m^3 and $1,000 \text{ m}^3$, the reverberation time requirement is determined by $T = (0.32 \times \lg V) - 0.17$ in seconds for the Octave bands from 250 Hz to 2,000 Hz.

Deviations of $\pm 20\%$ from the requirements in the individual octave bands are permitted.

The determination of the reverberation time must be based on the state of the art.

- **Noise reduction requirements**

For rooms that have requirements for noise reduction in order to protect the user (e.g. work rooms, workshops and corridors in schools, kindergarten rooms, break rooms, dining rooms, gymnasiums, swimming and sports halls), the following minimum requirement for noise reduction must be observed:

a) The mean sound absorption coefficient of the boundary surfaces (empty room, planning value) in the octave bands from 250 Hz to 4000 Hz has to be at least $\alpha_{m,B} = 0.20$ and for the octave band center frequencies of 500, 1,000 and 2,000 Hz, if possible, $\alpha_{m,B} = 0, 25$.

b) The mean sound absorption coefficient $\alpha_{m,B}$ must be determined according to the state of the

A deviation from these requirements is permitted if, for understandable operational or other technical reasons (e.g. hygiene), the arrangement of absorbent surfaces is not possible to the required extent.

- **ÖNORM B 8115, 1-7**

- 1) ÖNORM B 8115-1: 2011-06-01:
Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction –
Part 1: Definitions and units
- 2) ÖNORM B 8115-2: 2006-12-01:
Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction –
Part 2: Requirements for sound insulation
Subsequent version 2021-01-01, Part 2: Methodology for determining noise
protection levels
- 3) ÖNORM B 8115-3: 2005-11-01:
Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction –
Part 3: Architectural acoustics
- 4) ÖNORM B 8115-4: 2003-09-01:
Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction –
Part 4: Measures to fulfill the requirements on sound insulation
- 5) ÖNORM B 8115-5: 2012-04-01:
Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction –
Part 5: Classification
Subsequent version 2021-01-01, Part 5: Classification
- 6) ÖNORM B 8115-6: 2011-07-01:
Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction –
Part 6: Measuring methods to prove that the technical acoustic insulation
requirements in buildings have been fulfilled
- 7) ÖNORM B 8115-7: 2012-01-01:
Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction –
Part 7: Rating of impact sound insulation by floor coverings on a standard solid
timber floor

In most cases the OIB-5 Guidelines follow the national standards and summarize the most important regulations for common building situations. For different cases or further information, the national standards are to be consulted.

SOUND INSULATION REQUIREMENTS IN ITALY

- **Buildings Acoustics Reference Standard: DPCM 5.12.1997**

The D.P.C.M. 5.12-1997 is the reference document in the Italian legislation for building acoustics. It defines the performance that buildings must have regarding:

- Isolation from airborne noise between different real estate units
- Isolation from external noise
- Impact sound insulation
- Noise insulation of continuous and discontinuous systems

Compliance with acoustic requirements must be verified on site once the building is completed. As it concerns requirements related to sound insulation and installation noise, the following quantities are considered:

R'_w : sound reduction index (separating elements between dwellings)

$D_{2m,nT,w}$: standardized façade sound insulation

L'_{nw} : normalized impact sound insulation of floors

L_{ASmax} : maximum noise level for building services (discontinuous operation)

L_{Aeq} : maximum noise level for building services (continuous operation)

Table 6: Acoustic performance requirements defined in the D.P.C.M. 05.12.1997

Category	R'_w	$D_{2m,nT,w}$	$L'_{n,w}$	L_{ASmax}	L_{Aeq}
D	55	45	58	35	25
A, C	50	40	63	35	35
E	50	48	58	35	25
B, F, G	50	42	55	35	35

Cat. A: residential buildings;

Cat. B: office buildings;

Cat. C: hotels;

Cat. D: hospitals, clinics, nursing homes;

Cat. E: schools (all levels);

Cat. F: recreational or religious activities;

Cat. G: commercial activities;

While parameters such as apparent sound reduction index, façade sound insulation and normalized impact sound insulation depend on the characteristics of the building components, limitations concerning installation noise do not – and therefore cannot be considered as requirements that qualify construction solutions.

- **KLIMAHaus NATURE Certification**

Within the framework of the KlimaHaus certification system, the “Nature” certification calls for higher standards compared to the national regulations:

Table 7: Acoustic performance requirements for the Klimahaus Nature certification

Category	R'_w	$D_{2m,nT,w}$	$L'_{n,w}$	L_{ic}	L_{id}
A (residential buildings)	50	40	58	32	35
B (office buildings)	50	42	55	32	35

Where L_{ic} and L_{id} refer to the installation noise for continuous and discontinuous operation respectively and are defined in UNI 11367:2010. Compared to national regulations, stricter requirements are defined for impact sound insulation, as a limit value of 58 dB is set, compared to the 63 dB of the national standard.

- **Acoustic Classification of Buildings – UNI 11367**

The Italian standards also foresees a voluntary system of acoustic classification of buildings.

The acoustic class is to be considered an "intrinsic property of the building" and is therefore independent of the context in which it is located (external noise, building use, etc.).

The acoustic classification refers to the real estate units on the basis of the average values of the acoustic performance of its components measured on site. For each single real estate unit, one must test the acoustic performance of the horizontal and vertical partitions, of the facades, and the sound level introduced by the systems for continuous and discontinuous operation. The values measured for each individual quantity must therefore be averaged using a logarithmic mean. That means that it is possible that individual components of the building are characterized by an acoustic performance lower than the limit of the class, as long as the average value of the sample still respects this limit. The limit values for acoustic classification are reported in subsequent Table.

Table 8: Limit values associated to the acoustic classes

Acoustic class	R'_w	$D_{2m,nT,w}$	$L'_{n,w}$	L_{ic}	L_{id}
I	≥ 56	≥ 43	≤ 53	≤ 25	≤ 30
II	≥ 53	≥ 40	≤ 58	≤ 28	≤ 33
III	≥ 50	≥ 37	≤ 63	≤ 32	≤ 37
IV	≥ 45	≥ 32	≤ 68	≤ 37	≤ 42

The standard introduces the evaluation of the measurement uncertainty and, limited to the case of buildings with serial typological characteristics (for example, hotels, hospitals, etc.), of the sampling uncertainty. To take precautionary account of the uncertainty of building acoustic measurements, all the results of the measurements must be corrected with the values below. This means to increase the performance limit defined for the different classes by one or more decibels.

Table 9: Expanded uncertainty to apply to the result of acoustic measurements

	R'_w	$D_{2m,nT,w}$	$L'_{n,w}$	L_{ic}	L_{id}
Measure uncertainty	1	1	1	1.1	2.4

Schools and hospitals are not subject to acoustic classification. For these kinds of buildings, two performance levels are identified based on the performance of building components and installation noise.

Table 10: Reference value of acoustic performance for schools and hospitals

	R'_w	$D_{2m,nT,w}$	$L'_{n,w}$	L_{ic}	L_{id}
Base performance	50	38	63	32	39
Superior performance	56	43	53	28	34

	$D_{nT,w}$ (superimposed)	$D_{nT,w}$ (adjacent)	$L'_{n,w}$ (superimposed)
Base performance	50	45	63
Superior performance	55	50	53

It should be noted that the norm introduces the assessment of sound insulation between rooms of the same real estate unit, or between classrooms or hospital rooms. The DPCM 5/12/97, with the clause to report the evaluation of soundproofing power apparent only to the partitions between distinct real estate units, in fact, excluded from the verification the partitions between classrooms and between hospital rooms (such as those between the offices).

Once the acoustic class of the real estate unit has been determined, the overall acoustic class of the real estate unit can be defined, which is obtained as the average of the coefficients associated to each class, as reported below.

Table 11: Weight coefficients associated to the different classes for the evaluation of the global acoustic class of the real estate unit

Class	I	II	III	IV	*	**
Coefficient	1	2	3	4	5	10

* Performance up to 5 dB worse compared to class IV

** Performance more than 5 dB worse compared to class IV

The standard UNI 11367:2010 also specifies that, in environments where acoustic comfort, and specifically speech intelligibility, are of fundamental importance (classrooms, conference rooms, etc.) and/or where the control of sound absorption is critical (gyms, swimming pools, sports environments in general) it is necessary to determine the parameters C_{50} (clarity) and STI (Speech Transmission Index). In particular, for spaces dedicated to speech, the following limits hold: $C_{50} > 2$ dB and $STI > 0,6$.

1.1 Differences between Italian and Austrian standards

There are major differences concerning the approach, the limits and the indices that are used to define minimum requirements between the two countries. A few points are listed below:

Comparing the acoustic requirements across Europe and considering countries that use the same quantities to evaluate sound insulation, Austrian standards are among the strictest regulations, both as it concerns impact sound insulation and airborne sound insulation. Conversely, Italy has one among the laxest regulation.

Table 12: Differences in Italian and Austrian standards on acoustics

Austria	Italy
Sound insulation of facades: prescriptions depend on the external noise level	Sound insulation of facades: prescriptions do not depend on the external noise level
Prescriptions are made on building components (f.e. minimum values of sound insulation of wall and floor solutions are required without considering flanking transmission). Then, the performance of the chosen solution must be tested onsite	Only the final performance of the solution must be tested on site. (The existence of prescriptions concerning building elements can be of great usefulness for practitioners to orient the choice of the construction solutions)
Requirements concerning airborne sound insulation are expressed in terms of $D_{nT,w}$. For the impact sound insulation, $L_{nT,w}$ is proposed in the Austrian standards. The definition of all parameters is based on EU standards.	Requirements concerning airborne sound insulation are expressed in terms of R_w . For the impact sound insulation, L_{nw} is proposed in the Italian standards. The definition of all parameters is based on EU standards.
Requirements on components are the same for the different building uses. The only exception is represented by acoustic requirements on doors (variation depending on the use)	Requirements get stricter for certain categories of buildings, f.e. schools, hospitals, commercial activities
Parameter R_{res} indicates the resulting sound insulation of a building component comprising glazed elements, opaque elements and doors. This value is calculated based on the sound insulation of the elements, and not measured onsite (might seem misleading, as in EU standard it is used to indicate measurements that include flanking transmission effects)	

1.2 Acoustic standards in high-volume and high-rise timber constructions – Definition of minimum requirements in Italy and Austria

- **Structural noise protection:**

- **Requirements for the sound insulation of external components**

For residential buildings, homes, hotels, schools, kindergartens, hospitals, spa buildings, etc., as well as for administration and office buildings and the like the sound insulation of the exterior components of common rooms must not fall below the following values:

Table 13: Requirements for the sound insulation of external components

BIGWOOD SUGGESTION:							
Minimum required sound insulation of external components for residential buildings, homes, hotels, schools, kindergartens, hospitals, health resorts, etc.							
Minimum required sound insulation of external components for administration and office building, etc.							
Significant external noise level [dB]	Total external components [dB]	Opaque external components [dB]	Windows and doors [dB]		Ceilings and walls against unfinished attic spaces [dB]	Ceilings and walls against passageways and garages [dB]	Building partition walls at neighboring property or building site boundaries (each wall) [dB]
		External wall, roof Internal wall $R'_w \geq 44$ dB	Depending on size of window Without/with anteroom (door)				
<i>No substructure</i>	$R'_{res,w}$	R_w	R_w	$R_w + C_{tr}$	R'_w	R_w	R_w
	≥ 43	≥ 48	≥ 33	≥ 42/33	≥ 48	≥ 60	≥ 48

- **Requirements for airborne sound insulation within buildings**

Walls, ceilings and fixtures between rooms are to be dimensioned in such a way that the following values of the assessed standard sound level difference $D_{nT,w}$ do not fall below the following values due to the sound transmission through the separating component and the longitudinal sound line, e.g. the flanking components:

Table 14: Requirements for airborne sound insulation within buildings

BIGWOOD SUGGESTION:			
Minimum assessed standard sound level difference $D_{nT,w}$ in buildings			
Requirements on party walls, ceilings (external, separating)			
of	to	$D_{nT,w}$ [dB]	
1-3	All types	Walls without connection through doors, windows or other apertures	≥ 55
		Walls with connection through doors, windows or other apertures	≥ 50
		Ceilings	≥ 55

- **Requirements for impact sound insulation in buildings**

The assessed standard impact sound level $L'_{nT,w}$ in rooms must not exceed the following values:

Table 15: Requirements for impact sound insulation in buildings

BIGWOOD SUGGESTION:			
Maximum permissible assessed standard impact sound level $L'_{nT,w}$			
of	to	$L'_{nT,w}$ [dB]	
1	Common rooms	Rooms for other usage units (apartments, schools, kindergartens, hospitals, hotels, homes, administration and office buildings and comparable uses)	≤ 48
		Generally accessible terraces, roof gardens, balconies, loggias and attics	≤ 48
1	Adjoining rooms	Rooms for other usage units (apartments, schools, kindergartens, hospitals, hotels, homes, administration and office buildings and comparable uses)	≤ 53
		Generally accessible terraces, roof gardens, balconies, loggias and attics	≤ 53

2. Building standards and quality requirements in Italy and Austria – Thermal protection, energy consumption and moisture protection

Standards and guidelines:

Austria:

- OIB-6 Guidelines
- Tiroler Bauordnung 2001 (*LGBl. Nr. 94/2001 i.d.F. LGBl. Nr. 187/2014*)
- Techn. Bauvorschriften 2008 (*Landesgesetzblatt Nr. 93/2007 i.d.F. LGBl. Nr. 78/2013*)
- ÖNORM B 8110, part 5, 6
- Passivhaus Standards

Italy:

- UNI/TS 11300-1: Energy performance of buildings - Determination of the thermal energy demand for summer and winter conditioning
- UNI/TS 11300-2: Energy performance of buildings - Determination of primary energy requirements and yields for winter air conditioning, for the production of domestic hot water, for ventilation and for lighting in non-residential buildings
- UNI/TS 11300-3: Energy performance of buildings - Determination of primary energy requirements and yields for summer air conditioning
- UNI 10349 - Heating and cooling of buildings - Climatic data
- DM 26.06.2015 - Application of methodologies for calculating energy performance and defining the prescriptions and minimum requirements of buildings
- DGP 235/2020 – Energy Bonus (South Tyrol)

Reference EN/ISO standards:

- ISO 13789 – Thermal performance of buildings – Transmission and ventilation heat transfer coefficients – Calculation method
- ISO 6946 – Building components and building elements – Thermal resistance and thermal transmittance – Calculation methods
- ISO 10077 – Thermal Performance of windows, doors, shutters – Calculation of thermal transmittance
- ISO 10211 - Thermal bridges in building construction - Heat flows and surface temperatures - Detailed calculations
- ISO 13788 - Hygrothermal performance of building components and building elements - Internal surface temperature to avoid critical surface humidity and interstitial condensation - Calculation methods
- ISO 13370 - Thermal performance of buildings - Heat transfer via the ground - Calculation methods
- ISO 14683 - Thermal bridges in building construction - Linear thermal transmittance - Simplified methods and default values
- EN 12831 - Energy performance of buildings - Method for calculation of the design heat load

- ISO 52016 - Energy performance of buildings - Energy needs for heating and cooling, internal temperatures and sensible and latent heat loads
- ISO 9972 - Thermal performance of buildings - Determination of air permeability of buildings - Fan pressurization method.

Terms and units:

- U Heat transfer coefficient [W/m^2K]
- d Thickness of component layer [m]
- λ Thermal conductivity of component layer [W/mK]
- R_{si}, R_{se} Internal and external heat transfer resistance [m^2K/W]
- $HWB_{Ref,RK,zul}$ Annual heating demand [kWh/m^2a] for a reference building acc. to
- $KB_{RK,zuk}$ Annual cooling demand [kWh/m^2a] for a reference building acc. to
- $EEB_{RK,zul}$ Final energy requirement
- $F_{GEE,RK,zul}$ Overall energy efficiency factor [-]
- l_c Characteristic length, $l_c = V/A$; Compactness = A / V
V... heated gross volume [m^3], A... surface of thermal build. envelope [m]
- GFA Gross floor area [m^2]
- NFA Net floor area [m^2]
- H'_T Heat transfer coefficient for transmission [W/m^2K]; $H_{tr,adj}$ [W/K]
- $A_{sol,est}$ Summer equivalent area of the building [m^2]
- EP Energy performance indices $EP_{H,nd}$, $EP_{C,nd}$ and $EP_{gl,tot}$
(limit values for reference building $EP_{H,nd,lim}$, $EP_{C,nd,lim}$ and $EP_{gl,tot,lim}$,
reference scale for energy classification $EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$)
- η Building system efficiencies η_H , η_W and η_C
(limit values for reference building $\eta_{H,lim}$, $\eta_{W,lim}$ and $\eta_{C,lim}$)
- X_{real} Energy performance parameters of the real building; ref. building X_{Lst}

Requirements on building physics and energy efficiency in Austria

According to the Austrian OIB-6 guidelines (28 pages) and the ÖNORM B 8110, part 2-8 the subsequent requirements concerning thermal protection and energy consumption must be adhered.

The OIB-6 guideline applies to conditioned buildings, the process energy required in buildings is not included. Process energy is understood to be that energy that is used to satisfy other energy needs than the conditioning of rooms for use by people (e.g. conditioning of stables, cooling of technical rooms, heating of glass houses).

No Energy Performance Certificate is required for the following buildings:

- buildings that are only kept frost-free, i.e. with a room temperature of not more than +5°C, as well as unconditioned buildings,
- temporary buildings with a useful life of up to two years,
- residential buildings which, according to their type, are only intended for use during a limited period of time per calendar year and whose expected energy requirement is less than a quarter of the energy requirement for year-round use due to this restricted period of use (i.e. residential buildings used not more than 31 days between 1st November and 31st of March),
- buildings for operating facilities as well as agricultural utility buildings, in which the predominant proportion of the energy for space heating and cooling is covered by waste heat that is generated directly in the operating facilities,
- buildings used as a church or for religious purposes
- buildings and parts of buildings that are officially protected as part of a designated environment or due to their special architectural or historical value, insofar as compliance with these requirements would mean an unacceptable change in their character or their external appearance.

Still in this case an Energy Performance Certificate needs to be issued.

The calculation of the key energy figures must be carried out in accordance with the OIB guidelines “Energy-related behavior of buildings”. The number formats for the individual sizes can be found in the sample energy certificates in the appendix of the OIB-6 guideline.

- **Building categories:**

The categorization to one of the following building categories is based on the predominant usage, provided that other uses do not exceed 250 m² net floor space. If a net floor area of 250 m² is exceeded for one use, proceed as follows:

Either a division of the building and an assignment of the individual parts of the building to the building categories listed below must be carried out, or the entire building must be calculated several times for the various categories. In both cases, the requirement is checked separately depending on the building category.

Residential buildings (WG)

- 1) Residential buildings with 1-2 utilization units
- 2) Residential buildings with 3-9 utilization units
- 3) Residential buildings with ≥ 10 utilization units

Non-residential buildings (NWG)

- 4) Office buildings
- 5) Educational building
- 6) Hospitals
- 7) Homes
- 8) Hotels, Hostels, Inns
- 9) Restaurants/Public houses
- 10) Multiple purpose buildings
- 11) Sports buildings
- 12) Stores

Other types of energy-consuming buildings (SKG)

- 13) Other conditioned buildings

For residential buildings (WG) and non-residential buildings (NWG) normative usage profiles are available.

- **Requirements for the building:**

For both residential buildings (WG) and non-residential buildings (NWG) proof of compliance with the requirements for the reference climate is provided

Proof of the requirement for key energy figures can be provided either by fulfilling the final energy requirement or by the overall energy efficiency factor.

Nearly zero energy building

In the implementation of Directive 2010/31 / EU, a nearly zero-energy building is a building that meets the requirements of the "National Plan" (OIB document for the definition of the lowest-energy building and for setting intermediate targets in a national plan in accordance with Article 9 (3) to 2010/31 / EU from February 20, 2018).

After December 31, 2020, new buildings must be zero-energy buildings as defined in Article 2, Number 2 of Directive 2010/31 / EU (energy performance of buildings).

This aims to improve the energy performance of buildings in the European Union (EU), considering various climatic and local conditions. It sets out minimum requirements and a common framework for calculating energy performance. Following a review of its implementation, Directive 2010/31/EU was amended in 2018 by Directive (EU) 2018/844. The principal aim was to accelerate the cost-effective renovation of existing buildings and to promote smart technologies in buildings. As part of the Clean Energy package, the amending directive complements legislation on energy efficiency.

The building sector in the EU is the largest single energy consumer in Europe, absorbing 40% of energy, and about 75% of buildings are energy inefficient. Given these poor energy efficiency levels, decarbonizing the building stock is one of the EU's long-term goals. This directive is an important element in making buildings more efficient.

For further information, see also eur-lex.europa.eu

- **Requirements for energy indicators for new buildings and major renovations**

Residential buildings (WG, building categories 1-3) –

The compliance with the requirements for residential buildings can be provided fulfilling the final energy requirements or using the overall energy efficiency factor (maximum values in table below).

Table 16: Energy indicators for new buildings and major renovations (residential buildings)

Residential buildings (WG) (Building categorie 1-3)	New building	Major renovation	
HWB _{Ref,RK,zul} in [kWh/m ² a]	12 x (1 + 3,0 / I _c)	19 x (1 + 2,7 / I _c)	from entry into force
	10 x (1 + 3,0 / I _c)	17 x (1 + 2,9 / I _c)	from 01/01/2021
EEB _{RK,zul} in [kWh/m ² a]	EEB _{WG,RK,zul}	EEB _{WGsan,RK,zul}	from entry into force

Residential buildings (WG) (Building categorie 1-3)	New building	Major renovation	
HWB _{Ref,RK,zul} in [kWh/m ² a]	16 x (1 + 3,0 / I _c)	25 x (1 + 2,5 / I _c)	from entry into force
f _{Gee,RK,zul}	0,80	1,00	from entry into force
	0,75	0,95	from 01/01/2021

For non-residential buildings (NWG, building categories 4-12) the maximum values for final energy demand and the overall energy efficiency factor are shown in the subsequent tables.

Table 17: Energy indicators for new buildings and major renovations (non-residential buildings)

Non-residential buildings (WG) (Building categorie 4-12)	New building	Major renovation	
HWB _{Ref,RK,zul} in [kWh/m ² a]	12 x (1 + 3,0 / l _c)	19 x (1 + 2,7 / l _c)	from entry into force
	10 x (1 + 3,0 / l _c)	17 x (1 + 2,9 / l _c)	from 01/01/2021
KB* _{RK,zul} in [kWh/m ³ a]	1,0	2,0	from entry into force
EEB _{RK,zul} in [kWh/m ² a]	EEB _{NWG,RK,zul}	EEB _{NWGsan,RK,zul}	from entry into force
¹⁾ ... based on a storey height of 3.00m with the following usage profile: Building category 2 for buildings with GFA ≤ 1000 m ² ; Building category 3 for buildings with GFA > 1000 m ²			

Non-residential buildings (WG) (Building categorie 4-12)	New building	Major renovation	
HWB _{Ref,RK,zul} in [kWh/m ² a]	16 x (1 + 3,0 / l _c)	25 x (1 + 2,5 / l _c)	from entry into force
KB* _{RK,zul} in [kWh/m ³ a]	1,0	2,0	from entry into force
f _{Gee,RK,zul}	0,80	1,00	from entry into force
	0,75	0,95	from 01/01/2021
¹⁾ ... based on a storey height of 3.00 m with the following usage profile: Building category 2 for buildings with GFA ≤ 1000 m ² ; Building category 3 for buildings with GFA > 1000 m ²			

The OIB Guideline 6 uses the l_c-value in formulas regarding requirements for the heating demand HWB of buildings. The dependency of a limit value on the l_c-value requires that larger - and therefore more compact buildings have to adhere to a stricter limit value than smaller and less compact buildings.

The formulas in tables above express the compensation of the requirement for small-volume (e.g.: single-family houses) and large-volume (e.g.: apartment buildings, office buildings) types of construction and apply exclusively to the building authority approval procedure.

- **Calculation of the heating demand and the cooling demand acc. ÖNORM B 8110-6-1:2019**

The heating demand and the cooling demand of a building / part of a building may be calculated using the methods listed below.

- Dynamic procedures: Calculation method with detailed simulation or fully described simplified hour calculation method.
- Quasi-stationary method: monthly balance method.

It is expressly pointed out that the accuracy decreases according to the above order of the procedures. For verification procedures in Austria, the monthly balance procedure is the lowest level of accuracy.

The calculation of the heating requirement and the cooling requirement must be carried out in two separate steps, whereby the internal temperature is set at 22°C as the minimum temperature for heating and 26°C as the maximum temperature for cooling.

Annual heating demand

The annual heating demand Q_h is to be calculated as the sum of all months with actual heating:

$$Q_{h,a} = \sum_j Q_{h,j}$$

with

- $Q_{h,a}$ Annual heating demand of a building / part of a building; [kWh/a]
 $Q_{h,m}$ Monthly heating demand for reference or local climatic conditions; [kWh/m]

Monthly heating demand when calculated with reference climate conditions

The monthly heating demand when calculating with reference climate conditions $Q_{h,j,RK}$ is to be determined by balancing according to following equation:

$$Q_{h,j,RK} = (Q_{l,j} - \eta_{h,j} \cdot Q_{g,j}) \cdot f_h$$

with

- $Q_{h,j,RK}$ Monthly heating demand, calculated with reference climate conditions; [kWh/M]
 $Q_{l,j}$ Total heat losses in the respective month; [kWh/M]
 $\eta_{h,j}$ Degree of utilization for heat gains in the heating case in the respective month
 $Q_{g,j}$ Total heat gains in the respective month; [kWh/M]
 f_h Share in the respective month in heating mode with reference climate conditions

Monthly heating demand when calculated with local climate conditions

The monthly heating demand when calculating with local climate conditions $Q_{h,j,SK}$ is to be determined by balancing according to following equation:

$$Q_{h,j,SK} = (Q_{l,j} - \eta_{h,j} \cdot Q_{g,j}) \cdot \frac{d_{Heiz,j}}{MT_j}$$

with

$Q_{h,j,SK}$	Monthly heating demand, calculated with local climate conditions; [kWh/M]
$Q_{l,j}$	(Total) heat losses in the respective month; [kWh/M]
$\eta_{h,j}$	Degree of utilization for heat gains in the heating case in the respective month
$Q_{g,j}$	Total heat gains in the respective month; [kWh/M]
$d_{Heiz,j}$	Number of monthly heating days according to ÖNORM H 5056-1; [d]
MT_j	Number of days in the respective month

Annual cooling demand

The annual cooling demand Q_c is to be calculated as the sum of all months with actual cooling:

$$Q_{h,c} = \sum_j Q_{c,j}$$

with

$Q_{c,a}$	Annual cooling demand of a building / part of a building; [kWh/a]
$Q_{c,m}$	Monthly cooling demand for reference or local climatic conditions; [kWh/m]

Monthly cooling demand when calculated with reference climate conditions

The monthly cooling demand when calculating with reference climate conditions $Q_{c,j}$ is to be determined by balancing according to following equation:

$$Q_{c,j,RK} = f_{corr} \cdot (1 - \eta_{c,j}) \cdot Q_{g,j,c} \quad (\text{for } Q_{g,j,c} > Q_{l,j,c})$$

with

$Q_{h,j,RK}$	Monthly cooling demand, calculated with reference climate conditions; [kWh/M]
$Q_{g,j,c}$	Modified heat gains of a building / part of a building in the respective month; [kWh/M]
$Q_{l,j,c}$	Heat losses of a building / part of a building in the respective month; [kWh/M]
$\eta_{c,j}$	Degree of utilization for heat gains in the case of cooling in the respective month
f_{corr}	Correction factor (see ÖNORM B 8110-6.1:2019)

Monthly cooling demand when calculated with local climate conditions

The monthly cooling demand when calculating with local climate conditions is to be determined in the same way as for the reference climate conditions.

Specific, annual heating demand, based on the conditioned gross floor area

The specific annual heating requirement HWB_{BGF} related to the conditioned gross floor area is to be determined according to the following equation:

$$HWB_{BGF} = \frac{Q_{h,a}}{BGF}$$

with

HWB_{BGF} Specific, annual heating demand, based on the conditioned gross floor area; [kWh/m²·a]
 $Q_{h,a}$ Heating demand of a building / part of a building; [kWh/a]
 BGF Conditioned gross floor area (BGF = GFA); [m²]

Specific, annual heating demand for non-residential buildings, based on the gross floor height of 3.00 m

The specific annual heating requirement $HWB_{BGF,NWG}$ based on the gross floor height of 3.00 m is to be determined according to the following equation:

$$HWB_{BGF,NWG} = \frac{Q_{h,a}}{V/3}$$

with

HWB_{BGF} Specific, annual heating requirement, based on the gross floor height of 3.0m; [kWh/m²·a]
 $Q_{h,a}$ Heating demand of a building / part of a building; [kWh/a]
 BGF Conditioned gross volume; [m³]

Specific, annual cooling requirement, based on the conditioned gross floor area

The specific annual cooling requirement KB_{BGF} related to the conditioned gross floor area is to be determined according to the following equation:

$$KB_{BGF} = \frac{Q_{c,a}}{BGF}$$

with

KB_{BGF} Specific, annual cooling demand, based on the conditioned gross floor area; [kWh/m²·a]
 $Q_{c,a}$ Cooling demand of a building / part of a building; [kWh/a]
 BGF Conditioned gross floor area (BGF = GFA); [m²]

- **Climate model acc. ÖNORM B 8110-5-1:2019**

Reference climate

The calculation of the specific values according to ÖNORM B 8110-6-1 is based on the reference climate according to the following table.

Table 18: Reference climate Austria- ÖNORM B 8110-5-1:2019

Reference Climate (temperature and radiation values) – plain surfaces				
	January	February	March	April
Temperature	0,47°C	2,73°C	6,81°C	11,61°C
Radiation	29,79 kWh/m ²	51,42 kWh/m ²	83,40 kWh/m ²	112,81 kWh/m ²
	May	June	July	August
Temperature	16,20°C	19,33°C	21,12°C	20,56°C
Radiation	153,36 kWh/m ²	155,13 kWh/m ²	160,58 kWh/m ²	138,50 kWh/m ²
	September	October	November	December
Temperature	17,03°C	11,64°C	6,16°C	2,19°C
Radiation	98,97 kWh/m ²	64,35 kWh/m ²	31,47 kWh/m ²	22,34 kWh/m ²

For the reference climate θ_{ne} a standard outside temperature of -13°C can be assumed.

Figure 2: Temperature regions Austria
(Source: Central Institute for Meteorology and Geodynamics, Climate Department)

Local climate:

Monthly mean temperatures

The mean outside temperature in the respective month (monthly mean temperature) is mainly determined by the altitude. According to the climatology of Austria (ÖKLIM), the federal territory is divided into seven different regions with the corresponding mean, vertical temperature gradients (see subsequent figure). There are regional differences between the more maritime influenced west and the continental east of the country and north of the main Alpine ridge between foehn areas and those without foehn influence, also due to the alpine central location, the large basin landscapes in the south and the hilly landscapes on the eastern edge of the Alps.

Heating degree days

The heating degree days $HGT_{22/14}$ are to be calculated according to the following equation:

$$HGT_{22/14} = \sum_j (\theta_{i,h} - \theta_{e,i}) \cdot d_i$$

with

$HGT_{12/14}$ Heating degree days; [Kd/a]
 $\theta_{i,h}$ Mean internal temperature; [°C]
 $\theta_{e,i}$ Mean external temperature in the respective month; [°C]

$$\theta_e = a + b \cdot \frac{h}{100}$$

d_i Days per month with $\theta_{i,h} < 14^\circ\text{C}$; [d]

- Requirements for heat transferring components in new buildings (building categories 1 to 12)

For new buildings or parts of a buildings in building categories 1 to 12, the following heat transfer coefficients (U-values) must not be exceeded for conditioned rooms. For sloping ceilings with an incline of more than 60 degrees to the horizontal, the respective requirements for walls apply.

Table 19: U-value [W/m²K] of building components

Building components			U-Value [W/m ² K]
1	Walls	against outside air ¹⁾	0,35
2	Walls	against unheated or undeveloped attic spaces ¹⁾	0,35
3	Walls	against unheated parts of the building that must be kept frost-free (except lofts) and against garages ¹⁾	0,60
4	Walls	in contact with the ground ¹⁾	0,40
5	Walls	Walls (partition walls) between residential or business units or conditioned stairwells	1,30
6	Walls	against other structures at the borders of neighboring properties or building sites ¹⁾	0,50
7	Walls	Walls (partition walls) within residential and business units	[-]
8	Windows	also French doors and glazed doors in residential buildings (WG) against outside air ^{2,3)}	1,40
9	Windows	also French doors and glazed doors in non-residential buildings (NWG) against outside air ^{2,3)}	1,70
10	other transpar. components	vertical against outside air ⁴⁾	1,70
11	other transpar. components	horizontally or at an angle against outside air ^{4,5)}	2,00
12	other transpar. components	vertical against unheated building parts ⁴⁾	2,50
13	Roof windows	against outside air ^{5,6)}	1,70
14	Doors	unglazed, against outside air ⁷⁾	1,70
15	Doors	unglazed, against unheated parts of the building ⁷⁾	2,50
16	Doors	roller doors, sectional doors and the like against outside air ^{3,8)}	2,50
17	Int. Doors	internal doors (no further description)	[-]
18	Ceilings and slopes	each against outside air and against roof spaces (ventilated or uninsulated) ¹⁾	0,20
19	Ceilings	against unheated parts of the building ¹⁾	0,40
20	Ceilings	against separate living and business units ¹⁾	0,90
21	Ceilings	within residential and commercial units ¹⁾	[-]

22	Ceilings	above outside air (e.g. via passageways, parking decks) ¹⁾	0,20
23	Ceilings	against garages ¹⁾	0,30
24	Floors	in contact with the ground ¹⁾	0,40
<p>¹⁾ ... For walls, ceilings and floors in small areas against outside air, the ground and unheated parts of the building, the U-value may be up to twice the required value for 2% of the respective area. ²⁾ ... For windows the standard test dimension of 1.23 m x 1.48 m is to be used for the verification of the U-value, for French doors and glazed doors the dimension is 1.48 m x 2.18 m ³⁾ ... In particular for functional reasons (e.g. high-speed doors, automatic sliding entrance doors made of glass, revolving doors) this value may be exceeded in justified cases ⁴⁾ ... For large, glazed façade constructions, the dimensions for determination of the U-value must be limited by the planes of symmetry ⁵⁾ ... The defined requirement relates to the vertical installation situation, a conversion to the actual installation angle in relation to the fulfillment of the requirements of the U-value does not have to be carried out ⁶⁾ ... For roof windows, the standard test dimension of 1.23 m x 1.48 m is to be used to verify the U-value ⁷⁾ ... The test standard size 1.23 m x 2.18 m is to be used for doors ⁸⁾ ... The test standard size 2.00 m x 2.18 m is to be used for gates</p>			

- Requirements for heat-transferring components for individual measures on the building envelope

Maximum heat transfer coefficients (U-values) which are determined by one of the two following methods for conditioned rooms must not be exceeded for renovations (except major renovations) of buildings or building parts:

- a) A renovation concept is to be drawn up with the aim to achieve the requirements according to the requirements listed before.
- b) A renovation concept can be dispensed with if the maximum heat transfer coefficient for components of the (thermal) building envelope is undercut by at least 24%.

- Damaging condensation and risk of mold formation (acc. to ÖNORM B 8110-2:2020 Water vapor diffusion, water vapor convection and protection against condensation)

New constructions and renovations of buildings and parts of buildings, depending on their use (usage profile-specific moisture production) must avoid damage-causing condensation on the inner component surface and therefore minimize the risk of mold formation. Also, damage-causing condensation in the interior of components must be avoided.

Condensation protection in building construction means that all structural measures which are carried out under defined boundary conditions of the interior (temperature and humidity) and the relevant outside air conditions (temperature and humidity)

- secure a temperature on the room-side surface of the external components, so that there is no damaging water vapor condensation and mold growth is prevented
- prevent damaging water vapor condensation inside external components.

For the external components and components that separate rooms with different air conditions (temperature and relative humidity), the dimensioning can be carried out for a specific dimensioning climate:

- The structure of the component is dimensioned in such a way that the conditions to avoid damage-causing condensation, also with regard to the risk of mold formation are met on the surface on the room side.
- The structure of the component is dimensioned in such a way that no damage-causing water vapor condensation occurs inside the component.

In order to avoid condensation causing damage in practice, measures must be planned and implemented that influence the transport of liquid water (e.g. rainwater or building moisture) and the transport of water vapor through diffusion and convection in such a way that the moisture content that leads to damage, is avoided with sufficient certainty. In order to estimate the risk of damage in the planning, assumptions about the construction and the use of components are necessary:

- The components are airtight and windproof. This means that during a visual inspection no leaks can be seen in the layers that ensure air tightness or wind tightness. In the course of a leak search during a possible test of air permeability in accordance to ÖNORM B 9972, no leaks may be found that allow air to penetrate the interior of a component.
- During the construction phase, measures are taken to prevent additional moisture penetration (e.g. through rain) of the building materials. In the event of additional moisture penetration (e.g. from rain or installation water) during the construction phase, measures are taken to allow this moisture penetration to dry out without damage.
- The construction process and the room air conditions (temperature, relative humidity) on the construction site are suitable so that the times necessary for the drying of construction moisture (e.g. plasters, screeds, concrete) can be adhered to for a damage-free construction progress.
- The construction ensures that rainwater and other weather influences and also soil moisture do not cause moisture damage.
- Unconditioned rooms (e.g. cellars, winter gardens) are ventilated in such a way that the absolute air humidity corresponds to the outside air humidity.

- **Summer heat protection**

New buildings and major renovation of residential buildings (WG):

The summer heat protection is observed if the summer overheating is avoided or if there is no externally induced cooling requirement KB* for the most critical usage unit. Overheating in summer is avoided if for a daily periodic outdoor climate the operative temperature in the room does not exceed the value of

$$1/3 * T_{NAT,13} + 21.8^{\circ}C \quad (T_{NAT,13} = \text{location-dependent daily mean value}).$$

New buildings and major renovations of non-residential buildings (NWG).

Either overheating in summer is avoided (considering the actual internal loads), or the externally induced cooling requirement KB* must be observed

- **Air and wind tightness**

For new buildings, the building envelope must be airtight and windproof, with the air exchange rate $n_{50} \leq 3h^{-1}$ measured at a pressure difference of 50 Pa between the inside and outside, averaged over negative and positive pressure and with closed exhaust and supply air openings (acc. ÖNORM B 9972, Method 1).

If a mechanically operated ventilation system with or without heat recovery is installed, the air exchange rate n_{50} must not exceed $1,5h^{-1}$. For residential buildings (WG) of building category 1, as well as semi-detached and terraced houses, this value must be observed for every house respective every apartment or residential unit (BC 2 & 3). Averaging the individual apartments or residential units is not permitted. For non-residential buildings (NWG, BC 4-12), the requirements relate to each fire compartment.

- **Certificate of overall energy efficiency (Energy Performance Certificate):**

The following class limits are specified for the graphic representation in the energy efficiency scale on the first page of the Energy Performance Certificate:

Table 20: Energy Performance Certificate

Class	HWB _{Ref,SK} [kWh/m ² a]	PEB _{Ref,SK} [kWh/m ² a]	CO _{2eq,SK} [kg/m ² a]	f _{GEE,SK} [-]
A++	10	60	8	0,55
A+	15	70	10	0,70
A	25	80	15	0,85
B	50	160	30	1,00
C	100	220	40	1,75
D	150	280	50	2,50
E	200	340	60	3,25
F	250	400	70	4,00
G	> 250	> 400	> 70	> 4,0

- **ÖNORM B 8110, 1-8**

- 1) ÖNORM B 8110-1: 2008-01-01: RETRACTED!
Thermal protection in building construction - Part 1
- 2) ÖNORM B 8110-2: 2020-01-01 + BBL 1-4 (supplement 1-4):
Thermal protection in building construction -
Part 2: Water vapor diffusion, water vapor convection and protection against condensation
- 3) ÖNORM B 8110-3: 2020-06-01:
Thermal protection in building construction -
Part 3: Determination of the operating temperature in summer (Prevention of summerly overheating)
- 4) ÖNORM B 8110-4: 2011-07-15:
Thermal protection in building construction -
Part 4: Economic optimizing of thermal insulation
- 5) ÖNORM B 8110-5: 2019-03-15 + BBL 1-2 (supplement 1-2):
Thermal protection in building construction -
Part 5: Model of climate and user profiles
- 6) ÖNORM B 8110-6-1: 2019-01-15 & ÖNORM B 8115-6-2: 2019-11-01
+ BBL 1-5 (supplement 1-5):
Thermal protection in building construction -
Part 6-1: Principles and verification methods — Heating demand and cooling demand
Part 6-2: Principles and verification methods — Heating demand and cooling demand
— Examples for validation of the heating demand and cooling demand
- 7) ÖNORM B 8110-7: 2013-03-15:
Thermal protection in building construction -
Part 7: Tabulated design values for thermal insulation
- 8) ÖNORM B 8110-8: 2017-04-01:
Thermal protection in building construction -
Part 8: Tabulated design values for thermal insulation of construction components

In most cases the OIB-6 Guidelines follow the national standards and summarize the most important regulations for common building situations. For different cases or further information, the national standards are to be consulted.

- **Passivhaus Standards (PH)**

A building has been qualified as a passive house when it meets the following criteria set by the *Passive House Institute Darmstadt*:

(The reference value for the values listed is the net living space within the thermal building envelope.)

- **Annual heating demand (and cooling demand): max. 15 kWh/(m²a)**
- **Heating load: max. 10 W/m²**
- **Total primary energy demand: max. 60 kWh/(m²a)**
- **Pressure test air exchange / air tightness n_{50} : max. 0.6 h⁻¹**

These characteristics are achieved by the use of modern components, parts and efficient building technology:

- Thermal insulation
All opaque components of the outer shell of the house adhere a heat transfer coefficient (U-value) of max. 0.15 W/ m²K)
- Passive house windows
Windows (glazing including the window frames) do not exceed a U-value of 0.80 W/(m²K), with g-values around 50%
- Ventilation heat recovery
At least 75% of the heat from the exhaust air is returned to the fresh air by a heat exchanger. The comfort ventilation with the highly effective heat recovery results in good indoor air quality and saves energy
- Airtightness of the building
The leakage through uncontrolled joints must be less than 0.6 h⁻¹ in the test with a negative and positive pressure of 50 Pascal
- No thermal bridges
All edges, corners, connections and penetrations must be planned and executed with particular care in order to avoid thermal bridges or minimize them as much as possible

Requirements on building physics and energy efficiency in Italy

The European Community has indicated to member countries the way forward with the Directive 2002/91/EC "Energy performance in buildings" (EPBD, Energy Performance Buildings Directive), subsequently updated with Directive 2010/31/EU (EPBD2) and Directive 844/2018/EU.

Italy receives the indications of the directive through Legislative Decree 192/05, Law Decree 63/13 (converted by Law 90/13) and by the Ministerial Decree of 26.06.2015. Specific local regulations for South Tyrol implement Directive 844/2018 (DGP 235/2020).

- **Climate zones in Italy**

The Italian territory is divided into 6 climate zones, ranging from A to F based on the degree days.

Figure 3: Climate zones A-F, Italy (Source: celsiusanel.it)

- **Ministerial Decree 26.06.2015**

The DM 26.06.2015 covers different areas of application, namely: new construction, major renovations, energy retrofiting.

2. New construction

The “new construction” category includes:

- New buildings
- Demolition and reconstruction
- Extension of existing buildings with new technological building systems for which at least one of the following conditions holds: (i) The new gross air-conditioned volume is greater than 15 % of the gross existing air-conditioned volume or (ii) The new air-conditioned gross volume is greater than 500 m³. The enlarged part is in fact treated as a portion of new construction.

3. Major renovations

A “major renovation” is a renovation that involves over 25 % of the surface of the envelope of the entire building.

- Level I

The intervention affects more than 50 % of the total gross dispersing surface of the building; it also includes the renovation of the system for the winter and/or summer conditioning. The minimum requirements apply to the ENTIRE building.

- Level II

The intervention affects more than 50 % of the total gross dispersing surface of the building; it can also include the renovation of the system for the winter and / or summer air conditioning. The minimum requirements apply to the PORTION of building involved in the renovation.

4. Energy retrofiting

Interventions on the envelope or/and on the technological building systems that have an impact on the energy performance of the building, and which do not fall in previous cases.

The minimum requirements do not apply to:

- Buildings of historical architectural value and of historical-cultural value.
- Non-residential agricultural/industrial buildings if the rooms are heated for particular needs of the production process or using waste that cannot otherwise be used.
- Remake of portions of finish layers that are not influential from a thermal point of view (painting)
- Refurbishment of portions of plaster affecting an area of less than 10 % of the total gross dispersing surface of the building.
- Routine maintenance on existing heating systems.
- Rural non-residential buildings without air conditioning.
- Isolated buildings with a total useful area of less than 50 m².
- Boxes, cellars, garages, multi-storey car parks, depots, seasonal structures to protect sport facilities...
- Buildings used as places of worship and for religious activities.

Annex 2 of the DM 26.06.15 lists the requirements that are common to all interventions and the requirements that are specific for each of the categories presented above. In the following, a selection of these requirements is presented.

- **Requirements common to all interventions**

- **Condensation**

In the case of interventions concerning the opaque structures delimiting the conditioned volume towards the outside, in accordance with the technical standard EN ISO 13788, the technician must check the absence of:

- risk of mould formation, with particular attention to thermal bridges in new buildings (surface condensation);
- interstitial condensation.

Internal conditions should be set according to UNI EN ISO 13788 (humidity class method).

- **Thermal energy gains in summer**

To limit the energy requirements for summer air conditioning and to contain the internal temperature of the rooms, as well as to limit the overheating on an urban scale, for the roofing structures of the buildings it is mandatory to verify the effectiveness, in terms of cost/benefit ratio, of using:

- Materials with high solar reflectance for roofs (cool roofs), assuming for the latter a solar reflectance value of not less than 0.65 in the case of flat roofs and 0.30 in the case of pitched roofing.
- Passive air-conditioning technologies (by way of example and not limited to: ventilation, green roofs, ...).

- **Requirements for new buildings or major (Level I) or ZEB**

- **Transmission losses**

Global heat transfer coefficient

The DM 26.06.2015 indicates maximum values of H'_T [W/m²K] as reported in the following table:

Table 21: Global heat transfer coefficient (DM 26.06.2015)

SHAPE FACTOR	CLIMATE ZONE				
	A, B	C	D	E	F
$S/V > 0.7$	0.58	0.55	0.53	0.50	0.48
$0.7 > S/V > 0.4$	0.63	0.60	0.58	0.55	0.53
$0.4 > S/V$	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.75	0.70

Where the heat transfer coefficient for transmission H'_T is defined as,

$$H'_T = \frac{H_{Tr,adj}}{\sum_k A_k}$$

Where $H_{tr,adj}$ [W/K] is given as:

$$H_{Tr,adj} = H_D + H_G + H_U + H_A$$

with

- H_D Heat transfer coefficient for transmission from the heated space to the outside through the building envelope
- H_U Heat transfer coefficient for transmission from the heated space through the unconditioned space to the outside
- H_G Heat transfer coefficient for transmission from the heated space to the ground
- H_A Heat transfer coefficient for transmission from the heated space to an adjacent heated space held at a significantly different internal temperature

- **Thermal transmittance: separation walls**

The separation walls between neighbouring buildings or units (without prejudice to the compliance of passive acoustic requirements) must be characterized by transmittance values:

- $U \leq 0.8$ W/m²K (partition walls)
- $U < 2.8$ W/m²K (transparent elements)

Same limit values hold for the structures that delimit unheated rooms to the external environment (if they are also adjacent to heated rooms).

- **Summer equivalent solar area**

The summer equivalent area $A_{sol,est}$ of the building is calculated as the sum of the summer equivalent areas of each glazed component k :

$$A_{sol,est} = \sum_k F_{sh,gl} \cdot g_{gl+sh} \cdot (1 - F_F) \cdot A_{w,p} \cdot F_{sol,est}$$

All “known” parameters refer to the month of July. $F_{sol,est}$ is the correction factor for the incident radiation, obtained as the ratio between the average irradiance in July, in the location and on the exposure considered, and the average annual horizontal irradiance in Rome.

Table 22: Summer equivalent solar area – correction factor (DM 26.06.2015)

Building type	All climate zones
Residential buildings and similar	≤ 0.030
All other buildings	≤ 0.030

- **Energy performance indices**

The $EP_{H,nd}$, $EP_{C,nd}$ and $EP_{gl,tot}$ indices are lower than the values of the corresponding limit indices calculated for the reference building ($EP_{H,nd,lim}$, $EP_{C,nd,lim}$ and $EP_{gl,tot,lim}$)

$$EP_{H,nd} < EP_{H,nd,lim}$$

$$EP_{C,nd} < EP_{C,nd,lim}$$

$$EP_{gl,tot} < EP_{gl,tot,lim}$$

- **Building system efficiencies**

The efficiencies η_H , η_W and η_C are higher than the values of the corresponding efficiencies indicated for the reference building ($\eta_{H,lim}$, $\eta_{W,lim}$ and $\eta_{C,lim}$)

$$\eta_H > \eta_{H,lim}$$

$$\eta_W > \eta_{W,lim}$$

$$\eta_C > \eta_{C,lim}$$

- **Thermal energy gains in summer**

With the exception of buildings classified as E.6 (gyms, swimming pools) and E.8 (industrial activities), the technician should check, in all climatic zones with the exception of F, in places where the monthly average value of the horizontal irradiance in the month of maximum solar radiation, $I_{m,s} \geq 290 \text{ W/m}^2$:

- in relation to all vertical opaque walls with the exception of those included in the north-west/north/north-east quadrant, at least one of the following conditions, that the value of the surface mass M_s of the vertical opaque walls is greater than 230 kg/m^2 . Further the value of the periodic thermal transmittance module Y_{IE} is less than $0.10 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$.
- with respect to all the horizontal and angled walls that the value of the periodic thermal transmittance module Y_{IE} is less than $0.18 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$.

• **Requirements for major renovation (Level II)**

- **Transmission losses**

Global heat transfer coefficient

$$H'_T = \frac{H_{tr,adj}}{\sum_k A_k}$$

$$H_{tr,adj} = H_{T,ie} + H_{T,ig} + H_{T,iue} + H_{T,ij}$$

Maximum value of H'_T [$\text{W/m}^2\text{K}$]

Table 23: Shape factor in climate zones D - F (DM 26.06.2015)

SHAPE FACTOR	CLIMATE ZONE				
			D	E	F
M.REN. II level			0.68	0.65	0.62

- **Thermal transmittance**

The walls subject to intervention must have a transmittance lower than the limit provided for the energy retrofitting.

$$U < U_{lim}$$

- **Energy retrofitting**

- **Transmission losses**

The requirement is met if the thermal transmittance values of the components subject to intervention are lower than those in the table below.

Table 24: Thermal transmittance of building components (DM 26.06.2015)

CLIMATE ZONE	Thermal transmittance [W/m ² K]				
	Walls	Roofs	Floors	Windows	Partitions
A	0.40	0.32	0.42	3.00	0.80
B	0.40	0.32	0.42	3.00	0.80
C	0.36	0.32	0.38	2.00	0.80
D	0.32	0.26	0.32	1.80	0.80
E	0.28	0.24	0.29	1.40	0.80
F	0.26	0.22	0.28	1.00	0.80

- **Thermal transmittance: partition walls**

The separation walls between neighbouring buildings or units (without prejudice to the compliance of passive acoustic requirements) must be characterized by transmittance values:

- $U \leq 0.8 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ (partition walls)
- $U < 2.8 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ (transparent elements)

Same limit values hold for the structures that delimit unheated rooms to the external environment (if they are also adjacent to heated rooms).

- **Reference building**

The reference building is identical to the design building in terms of geometry (shape, volumes, surface, surfaces of construction elements and components), orientation, territorial location, intended use and boundary conditions but it has predetermined thermal characteristics and energy parameters.

Reference building method

- Determination of indices and energy performance parameters of the real building (X_{real})
- Determination of indices and energy performance parameters of the reference building (X_{Lst})
- Comparison and evaluation of values

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 EP_{H,nd} < EP_{H,nd,lim} & \eta_H > \eta_{H,lim} \\
 EP_{C,nd} < EP_{C,nd,lim} & \eta_W > \eta_{W,lim} \\
 Ep_{gl,tot} < EP_{gl,tot,lim} & \eta_C > \eta_{C,lim}
 \end{array}$$

The verification is satisfied if the indices and performance parameters of the real building are more performing than the corresponding indices determined for the reference building.

The “reference building method” is used to evaluate the energy performance of the buildings in the case of new buildings, buildings undergoing level I major renovations and ZEB.

Thermal transmittances of the reference building (2019/2021)

Table 25: Thermal transmittance of building components – reference building method

CLIMATE ZONE	Thermal transmittance [W/m²K]				
	Walls	Roofs	Floors	Windows	Partitions
A	0.43	0.35	0.44	3.00	0.80
B	0.43	0.35	0.44	3.00	0.80
C	0.34	0.33	0.38	2.20	0.80
D	0.29	0.26	0.29	1.80	0.80
E	0.26	0.22	0.26	1.40	0.80
F	0.24	0.20	0.24	1.10	0.80

- For separating elements to unheated rooms, the transmittance value must be divided by the $b_{tr,u}$ factor (UNI/TS 11300-1:2014).
- In the case of building elements facing the ground, the values of the respective tables must be compared with the equivalent thermal transmittance values calculated on the basis of UNI EN ISO 13370.
- The values of the transmittances of the reference building are inclusive of the effect of thermal bridges.
- For opaque elements towards the outside, the solar absorption coefficient of the real building is considered ($Q_{sol,op}$).
- For the glazed components, the global transmission factor of solar energy g_{gl+sh} , is assumed in the presence of a shielding (with orientation from East to West passing through South) equal to 0.35.

It is worth noticing that the reference building to be used to carry out control on minimum requirements (ER-RM) has different characteristics from those used to determine the energy certificate (ER-CE).

- **Energy classes**

To build the reference scale for the energy classification, it is necessary to determine the value of $EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$ for the reference building:

$$EP_{gl,nren,Lst} = EP_{H,nren,Lst} + EP_{W,nren,Lst} + EP_{V,nren,Lst} + EP_{C,nren,Lst} + EP_{L,nren,Lst} + EP_{T,nren,Lst}$$

Based on the value of $EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$ calculated for the reference building, used as a delimitation between class A1 and B, the classification scale is then constructed by applying the multiplicative factors highlighted in the following table.

Table 26: Thermal transmittance of building components (DM 26.06.2015)

	Class A4	$\leq 0,40 EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$
$0,40 EP_{gl,nren,Lst} <$	Class A3	$\leq 0,60 EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$
$0,60 EP_{gl,nren,Lst} <$	Class A2	$\leq 0,80 EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$
$0,80 EP_{gl,nren,Lst} <$	Class A1	$\leq 1,00 EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$
$1,00 EP_{gl,nren,Lst} <$	Class B	$\leq 1,20 EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$
$1,20 EP_{gl,nren,Lst} <$	Class C	$\leq 1,50 EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$
$1,50 EP_{gl,nren,Lst} <$	Class D	$\leq 2,00 EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$
$2,00 EP_{gl,nren,Lst} <$	Class E	$\leq 2,60 EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$
$2,60 EP_{gl,nren,Lst} <$	Class F	$\leq 3,50 EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$
	Class G	$> 3,50 EP_{gl,nren,Lst}$

- **CASA CLIMA Certification System**

The CasaClima certification is a process that can be split into 5 steps:

1. Request for construction permit
The first step is the request of the construction permit to the municipality.
2. Request for CasaClima certification
Before the start of the works, the request for certification is delivered to the CasaClima Agency of Bolzano (or to a Partner agency) together with all the documentation required by the CasaClima technical directive.
3. Checking the technical documentation
The CasaClima Agency performs the first checks on the project and, if there is no correspondence with the requirements of the Technical Directive, interfaces with the referring technician for corrections and additions.
4. Energy audit on site
During the construction phase, the CasaClima Agency instructs a CasaClima Auditor who will perform site inspections to verify that the execution of the works complies with the project presented and validated by the Agency itself.
5. Issue of the CasaClima certificate
At the end of the works, the CasaClima Agency performs the final check of the documentation and, if all the construction quality requirements defined by the reference technical directives are met, it issues the CasaClima certificate with the relative plate certifying the energy class and possibly the criteria of sustainability.

The CasaClima technical directive dealt with in the following refers to new construction – and in particular to the minimum requirements introduced by DGP 235/2020.

The minimum requirements refer to the characteristics and energy performance of the building envelope, the energy performance of the building and the use of renewable energy.

- **Energy Performance**

The energy performance of the building envelope must be equal to or higher than that of the CasaClima class A. The energy performance of the building must correspond to that of the CasaClima A class.

NOTE: A building in the CasaClima A or CasaClima Gold energy class corresponds to the definition of nZEB, pursuant to the European Directive 2010/31/EU Art.2, paragraph 2.

- Energy efficiency of the building envelope: $\leq 30 \text{ kWh/m}^2\text{a}$
- Overall energy efficiency: $\leq 30 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{m}^2\text{a}$ for the municipality of Bolzano.
- Carbon dioxide emissions of buildings with or without cooling (primary energy requirement equiv.) must be equal to or higher than the CasaClima Class A.
Without cooling: $\leq 20 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{m}^2\text{a}$
With cooling: $\leq 10 \text{ kg CO}_2/\text{m}^2\text{a}$

Klima Haus Klasse	Effizienz der Gebäudehülle (EGH _{WGB})	Äquiv. Primärenergiebedarf ohne Kühlung (PEH _{WGB})	Äquiv. Primärenergiebedarf Kühlung (PEK _{WGB})**	Gesamtenergieeffizienz (GEE _{WGB}) (= PEH _{WGB} +PEK _{WGB})
Classe Casa Clima	Efficienza Energetica Involucro (EIN _{RES})	Fabbisogno Energia Primaria Equiv. Senza Raffrescamento (EPSR _{RES})	Fabbisogno Energia Primaria Equiv. Raffrescamento (EPR _{RES})**	Efficienza complessiva (Prestazione energetica) (EEC _{RES}) (= EPSR _{RES} +EPR _{RES})
	[kWh/m ² a]	[kg CO ₂ eqv./m ² a]	[kg CO ₂ eqv./m ² a]	[kg CO ₂ eqv./m ² a]
Gold*	≤10	≤10	≤5	≤15
A*	≤30	≤20	≤10	≤30
B	≤50	≤35	≤15	≤50
C	≤70	≤50	≤20	≤70
D	≤90	≤65	≤25	≤90
E	≤120	≤90	≤30	≤120
F	≤160	≤120	≤40	≤160
G	>160	>120	>40	>160

Figure 4: Energy performance – Casa Clima certification system

The limits and classification of the energy efficiency of the envelope refer to the climatic data of the reference municipality of Bolzano. The limits and classification of overall efficiency are determined on the municipality of location.

- Additional requirements

Total primary energy requirement

The total primary energy requirement must be covered for at least 50 % by renewable energies. If the optimal level according to costs cannot be reached or when the building is built in the CasaClima Oro class, this requirement is eliminated.

Hot water requirement

The hot water requirement must be provided for at least 60 % using renewable energy. Alternatively, the overall primary energy requirement must be reduced by at least 25 % by improving the efficiency of the plant, object of the intervention. When a building covers its thermal energy needs by means of an electric heat pump or district heating, this requirement is eliminated.

Self-regulation for temperature control

Where technically and economically feasible, new buildings must be equipped with self-regulating deposits. The self-regulating devices separately control the temperature in each room or in justified cases, in a specific heated area of the property.

Transmittance limit values U (W/m²K)

Table 27: Transmittance – limit values U

Component	Limit value for buildings in climate zone E U [W/m ² K]	Limit value for buildings in climate zone F U [W/m ² K]
Vertical opaque structures towards the outside	0.34	0.33
Opaque horizontal / inclined structures: roof	0.30	0.29
Opaque horizontal / inclined structures: floors	0.33	0.32
Window glass	1.7	1.3
Total U-value of the window	2.2	2.0

Energy bonus

If a building is constructed according to the CasaClima A nature standard, the permissible building volume can be increased by 10 %. In the building permit, the use of the energy bonus must be explicitly mentioned.

Blower door test

The measurement of the air permeability (blower door test) is required both for new buildings and for retrofitting interventions. The limit values of the n_{50} (h⁻¹), describing the air changes at a differential pressure of 50 Pa, are defined based on the energy class:

Table 28: Blower door tests - Limit values n_{50}

CasaClima energy standard	n_{50} limit value
Gold	$\leq 0.6 \text{ h}^{-1}$
A	$\leq 1.5 \text{ h}^{-1}$
B	$\leq 1.5 \text{ h}^{-1}$
R	$\leq 3 \text{ h}^{-1}$

2.1 Differences between Italian and Austrian standards

There are differences concerning the approach, the limits and the indices that are used to define minimum requirements between the two countries.

Table 29: Building physics – differences in Italy and Austria

Austria	Italy
Shape factor (characteristic length $l_c = V/A$), influence of building compactness	Reference building method
Building categories; no subdivision new building and major renovations	No categories; subdivision new building, major renovation (I & II), energy retrofitting
Key values heating (and cooling) demand, final energy requirements and overall energy efficiency factor	Key value energy performance indices EP and building system efficiencies η
Fixed U-values for building components, for example Walls 0,35 W/m ² K Roofs 0,20 W/m ² K <i>Passivhaus:</i> <i>opaque structures towards the outside</i> <i>0,15 W/m²K</i>	U-values for building components depend on climate zones, for example Walls 0,28 (E) and 0,26 (F) W/m ² K Roofs 0,25 (E) and 0,22 (F) W/m ² K <i>CasaClima:</i> <i>vert. opaque structures towards the outside</i> <i>0,34 (E) and 0,33 (F) W/m²K</i> <i>hor. opaque structures towards the outside</i> <i>0,30 (E) and 0,29 (F) W/m²K</i>
Passivhaus: annual heating and cooling demand $\leq 15\text{kWh}/(\text{m}^2\text{a})$ (net living space) and $n_{50} < 0,6\text{h}^{-1}$	CasaClima Gold: energy efficiency of the building envelope $\leq 10\text{kWh}/(\text{m}^2\text{a})$ and $n_{50} < 0,6\text{h}^{-1}$

2.2 Quality standards in high-volume and high-rise timber constructions – Definition of minimum requirements in Italy and Austria

- **Structural thermal protection:**

- **Requirements for the thermal insulation of external components**

For building components such as walls, ceilings, roofs, floors, windows and doors the *Passivhaus* or rather *CasaClima* requirements shall be applied for all types of buildings in the northern parts of Italy (zones E and F) and Austria:

Table 30: BIGWOOD requirements on building physics

	BIGWOOD Requirements
Building components	Fixed U-values for building components <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - opaque structures towards the outside (walls, ceilings, roofs, ground floor) $U \leq 0,15 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ - partition structures (walls, ceilings) $U \leq 0,5 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ - transparent elements (windows, doors) $U \leq 0,8 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$
	No thermal bridges
Energy efficiency	Annual heating and cooling demand $Q \leq 15\text{kWh}/(\text{m}^2\text{a})$ (<i>net living space</i>) or energy efficiency of the building envelope $\leq 10 \text{ kWh}/(\text{m}^2\text{a})$
	Total primary energy demand: Max. $60\text{kWh}/(\text{m}^2\text{a})$
	Heating load max. $10 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$
Air tightness & ventilation	$n_{50} < 0,6\text{h}^{-1}$
	At least 75% of the heat from the exhaust air is returned to the fresh air by a heat exchanger

3. Building standards and quality requirements in Italy and Austria – Ecology and LCA

Standards and guidelines:

Austria:

- OIB-3 Guidelines
- Eco-Index OI3 (IBO2021)
- klimaaktiv Assessment
- ÖNORM B 1801-4

Italy:

- CasaClima (Nature) Certification System

EN/ISO:

- ISO 14040:2021-03-01 – Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – principles and framework
- ISO 14044:2021-03-01 – Environmental management – Life cycle assessment – requirements and guidelines
- ISO 14025:2006 – Environmental labels and declarations – Type III environmental declarations – principles and procedures
- EN 15804:2020-02-15 – Sustainability of construction works – Environmental product declarations – Core rules for the product category of construction products

REQUIREMENTS ON ECOLOGY AND LCA IN AUSTRIA

- **Eco-Index OI3:**

The "OI3 Index" assesses the ecologic quality of all applied building materials using environmental indicators.

- Global warming potential (GWP)
- Acidification potential (AP)
- Non-renewable demand for primary energy (PENRT)

The eco-index can be calculated for building materials, constructions and entire buildings. As a single figure, the indicator provides quantitative information on the potential for global warming, acidification of the environment and the consumption of non-renewable energy resources.

Benefits:

- No additional costs (and efforts)
- Individual details
- Summary of the most important environmental impacts
- Similar to determination of heating demand
- Evaluation – the lower the value, the better for the environment

For calculation and selection of ecological building products, a quality-assured database is available at www.baubook.at. The ecological quality of a construction product or a building is determined using ecological stress points indicated.

Class A means a very low and class E a very high ecological burden.

Figure 5: Ecology classes – OI3 Index

The calculations are based on the IBO guideline value table for building materials and can be calculated using various computer programs, e.g. eco2soft. Using a balance border method, it is possible to look at everything from the thermal building envelope (BG0) to an overall view of the building (BG6). The reference limits BG0 to BG3 are predominantly used in Austria. From the balance border BG3 onwards, the service lives are also taken into account for the component layers. This not only considers the actual construction of the building, but also the required renovation and maintenance cycles of the component layers during the building's lifetime. The standardized period under review is 100 years.

Basics of the OI3-assessment

The following OI3-basic indicators are defined:

- $\Delta OI3_{BS}$: eco-indicator of a building material layer
- $\Delta OI3_{KON}$: eco-indicator of a square meter of a construction
- $\Delta OI3$: eco-indicator for buildings

The OI3 comprises the three indicators global warming potential, acidification potential and the need for non-renewable energy.

The absolute values of the key figures are converted into a points system. The higher the number of points achieved, the more serious the construction or the building affects on the environment. Detailed information on the various OI3 indicators as well as exact calculation rules are in the current OI3 calculation guide on www.baubook.at/oekoindex.

Figure 6: OI3 assessment points of different materials

$\Delta OI3_{BS}$

The $\Delta OI3_{BS}$ of a building material layer within a component represents to how many OI3 points this building material layer increases or decreases the $\Delta OI3_{KON}$ value of the construction.

This $\Delta OI3_{BS}$ indicator is very helpful in the process of design optimization, as the "ecological heavyweights" of the construction can easily identified among at the highest $\Delta OI3_{BS}$ points.

$\Delta OI3_{KON}$

The ecological quality of common constructions is shown by the ecological indicator $\Delta OI3_{KON}$.

Reference to the OI3-building indicators:

The OI3-building indicators can be related to the gross floor area (GFA), the reference area (BZF, corresponds to the GFA and half the floor area of buffer rooms such as winter gardens) or the characteristic length l_c .

Example: Concrete external wall compared with a CLT-wall and a timber frame wall

Figure 7: Comparison of OI3- assessment of a concrete wall, a CLT-Wall and a timber frame wall

- **klimaaktiv assessment:**

The klimaaktiv building standard marks out buildings which combine top performance as regards energy and ecology with professional implementation. The klimaaktiv criteria are grouped in four assessment categories.

Figure 8: klimaaktiv assessment of Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology, Republic of Austria

Location and quality assurance

Choosing the location and defining the quality levels to be demonstrated provide the foundation for a building that operates sustainably. Here infrastructure facilities and environmentally sound mobility at the location are just as important as life-cycle costs, achieving air-tightness or registering the energy consumption data.

Energy and supply systems

Modest energy demand, low CO₂-emissions and a lower primary energy rating than in run-of-the-mill buildings are critical for achieving top klimaaktiv quality. Compliance with the standard can be calculated either to OIB-guideline 6 (2020) or to PHPP (Version 9).

Construction materials

Materials especially harmful to the climate and substances of very high concern are ruled out; employing environmentally friendly materials is rewarded. Ecological improvements, from producing a building all the way to disposing of it, are taken into account for klimaaktiv.

Comfort and indoor air quality

In summer-proof buildings with interiors constructed from low-emission materials, the indoor climate is pleasant and indoor air quality is good. Points are awarded for providing a ventilation system with heat recovery

The klimaaktiv catalogue covers all the criteria for the building standard; it exists for diverse types of building (with a distinction between new buildings and renovation) – residential accommodation, offices, educational and sports facilities, centers for functions, medical facilities and hospitals, hotels and B&Bs, supermarkets, retail and wholesale trading premises, large and small-scale industry. The criteria are publicly accessible and available free of charge.

On the basis of the criteria an individual combination of features that make sense for the building in question can be selected. A total of 1000 klimaaktiv quality points can be notched up. For the basic level, klimaaktiv Bronze, all the essential klimaaktiv criteria must be satisfied – these are considerably more demanding than the usual targets applying in the market for new buildings and renovation, inter alia as regards energy efficiency and primary energy demand.

Three quality levels exist:

- Bronze: buildings that satisfy all essential criteria
- Silver: buildings that satisfy all essential criteria and score at least 750 points
- Gold: buildings that satisfy all essential criteria and score at least 900 points

- A** Location and quality assurance
- B** Energy and supply systems
- C** Construction materials
- D** Comfort and indoor air quality

Figure 9: Assessment System of "klimaaktiv" buildings

Registering on the building platform

- If you wish to declare a klimaaktiv residential building for the first time, register free of charge on the klimaaktiv building platform *baubook.at/kahg* (in German).
- Once you have registered, you will be guided through the declaration procedure step by step and receive all the information you need. A declaration in progress can be interrupted at any time, continued later or aborted.

Defining your project

- First you must indicate whether the building is at the planning stage, has been completed or is already in use.
- All boxes marked with a * must be filled in. Once all the necessary entries have been made and the required proofs of compliance have been uploaded, a green tick will appear in the relevant status box as confirmation.

Completing the declaration

- Once all the necessary entries have been made on the five input sheets and all the necessary proofs of compliance have been uploaded, a green tick will appear in the overview. Now the declaration can be concluded. This automatically ends data input, and the file is passed on to the province's plausibility checker.

Plausibility check

- The plausibility checker and you each receive confirmation by email that your building is to be checked.
- If proofs of compliance or data in the declaration are insufficient, you will be informed of this via an email tool and can revise your declaration before resubmitting it for checking. If the checking process is successful, the project is given the green light.

Publishing the project

- Details of all klimaaktiv buildings are published on the building database *klimaaktiv-gebaut.at* (in German).

Badge and certificate

- Once your building has been completed, you will receive a certificate and a badge from the klimaaktiv program management.

- **Lifecycle assessments LCA on the product stage (EPD) European Product Declaration:**

A lifecycle assessment is a quantitative evaluation procedure. It evaluates the material and energy flows of building products, systems or processes according to the problems for the site, individual life stages or over the entire lifecycle. The international standards for the preparation of lifecycle assessments are defined in ISO 14040 and ISO 14044. Lifecycle assessments are part of Environmental Product Declarations – Type III environmental declarations according to ISO 14025 and EN 15804 and may, but do not have to, be used to assess the building product within the framework of ecolabels such as natureplus or the IBO mark of conformity. Last but not least, lifecycle assessments also enable manufacturers to optimize production processes.

Standardized assessments include life cycle assessments, environmental labels, environmental product declarations (EPD) and building certifications. Life cycle assessments depict a life cycle analysis. Environmental labels are primarily used to provide information to the end consumers. EPDs are intended for B2B communication and, strictly speaking, do not contain any evaluation. The use of construction products is assessed in building certifications.

Environmental product declarations (EPD) for building products provide data relating to the environment. An EPD can be used to prove that a product meets the basic requirements of the European Construction Products Regulation. Essentially, the procedure for EPD creation or verifying an EPD's content is regulated in ISO 14025 "Environmental labels and declarations – Type III environmental declarations – Principles and procedures" and in EN 15804 "Sustainability of construction works. Environmental product declarations. Core rules for the products category of building products".

The IBO models the lifecycle assessment, interprets and describes the underlying data and writes up both the background report on the EPD and, if required, the EPD texts for subsequent submission to an EPD platform.

The aim of the Austrian EPD platform for building products Bau EPD GmbH is to create a uniform basis for the preparation of lifecycle assessments in the construction sector. These efforts should lead to consistent, and thus comparable building material data, which can also be used in building evaluation systems.

Guide to calculating the "grey energy" of buildings:

The guide is part of an integrated assessment system for housing estates that is currently under development whose aim it is to operationalize the international climate protection targets for Austria. The Swiss assessment model of the 2000 W Society for Sites is used as a reference point.

In the context of the Urban Area Parameters 2017 project, first steps were taken to adapt the central building blocks to the Austrian framework conditions. The core of the project was to derive specific guideline values (per m²) and specific target values (per person) for the sectors "building operation", "grey energy" and "everyday mobility".

The guide for calculating the "grey energy" of buildings is part of the results. It strives to make an extensive uniform calculation of the "grey energy" of buildings over their lifecycle.

Figure 10: Types of EPD (Product Declaration) with respect to life cycle stages covered and lC-stages and modules for the construction works assessment - EN 15804 (A-D)

Countless products are offered by the construction industry. Most of the varied technical and aesthetic requirements are met, but also the life of a building is influenced and there is an impact on people and the environment. Assessments are necessary for making safe decisions about sustainable building and renovation.

- **Hygiene, health and environmental protection (OIB 3 Guidelines)**

Exhaust gases from fireplaces - General requirements for exhaust systems

All fireplaces are to be connected to exhaust systems that lead over the roof.

The outlets of exhaust systems are to be positioned in such a way that people are not harmed by exhaust gases and that proper draft conditions are guaranteed.

If the horizontal distance between the outlets of flue gas systems and ventilation openings of lounges (e.g. windows, doors, supply air openings of ventilation systems) is less than 10 m, the following minimum vertical distances must be observed:

- 3.00 m if the muzzle is in front of windows, doors or air intake openings,
- otherwise 1.00 m.

The mouth of the exhaust system must be above the windows, doors or air intake openings. The vertical distance between the upper edge of the muzzle and the lower edge of the lintel or the upper edge of the ventilation opening is to be measured.

The mouth must protrude from the ridge by at least 40 cm, or the following minimum distances from the roof surface, measured normally to it, must be observed:

- 60 cm for fireplaces operated with gas or oil in which the temperature of the flue gases is lowered below the dew point (condensing boiler),
- otherwise 1.00 m.

In the case of flat roofs, the opening must be at least 40 cm above the upper edge of the parapet and at least 1.00 m above the roof surface. If a roof area is used as a terrace, the opening must be at least 1.50 m above the stand area.

Protection from moisture

- from the soil

Structures with lounges and other structures, the purpose of which requires this, must be protected in all their parts against the ingress and rise of water and moisture from the ground.

- Protection against rainwater

The shell of structures with lounges as well as of other structures, the purpose of which requires this, must be designed in such a way that rainwater cannot penetrate into the structure of the external components and into the interior of the structure.

- Prevention of flooding

If the floor level of common rooms is not above the level of the hundred-year flood event, provision must be made for equivalent protection against flooding.

- Avoidance of damage caused by water vapor condensation

Space-delimiting components of structures with common rooms as well as other structures whose intended use requires this must be constructed in such a way that damage from water vapor condensation does not occur either in the components or on their surfaces during normal use. In the case of external components with low storage capacity (such as window and door elements), suitable measures must be taken to ensure that adjacent components are not soaked through

Protection against dangerous immissions

Concentration of pollutants

Lounges are to be designed in such a way that dangerous emissions from building materials and from the subsurface do not lead to concentrations that can impair the health of the users if the air exchange is appropriate for the purpose of use. In any case, this is considered to be fulfilled for building materials if building products are used as intended, which meet the national regulations on building products.

Radon emissions from the subsurface and ionizing radiation

Buildings with common rooms in radon prevention areas or radon protection areas are to be designed in such a way that radon ingress from the subsurface, which could endanger the health of the users, is prevented. In any case, this is deemed to have been met if the reference value of 300 Bq / m³ for the annual mean activity concentration of radon in the air is maintained in the living rooms.

Lounges are to be designed in such a way that no gamma radiation from building products, which could endanger the health of the user, occurs. Construction products that emit gamma radiation can be used if, taking into account all factors relevant for radiation protection, the reference value of 1 mSv per year for external exposure in living rooms to gamma radiation from construction products is observed in addition to external exposure in the open air.

Exposure and lighting

Exposure requirements

In common rooms, the entire light entry area (architectural lights from windows, skylights, skylights, etc.) must be at least 12% of the floor area of this room.

A sufficient free incidence of light for exposure must be guaranteed for the light entry surfaces required. This applies to the necessary light entry surfaces if a free angle of incidence of light of 45 degrees to the horizontal, measured from the facade or from the level of the roof cladding, is observed. This free incidence of light must not be swiveled sideways by more than 30 degrees.

If components (e.g. balconies, eaves, loggias, bay windows, protruding storeys) of the same building protrude into the required free incidence of light, the total light entry area must be at least 15% of the floor area of the room. This is not necessary if the protrusion of the component, measured from the facade alignment in the area of the respective light entry surface, is not more than 1.50 m.

The required light entry area increases from a room depth of more than 5.00 m by 1% of the total floor area of the room for each meter of additional room depth.

REQUIREMENTS ON ECOLOGY AND LCA IN ITALY

- **CASA CLIMA NATURE**

The CasaClima Nature certification is a sustainability assessment of buildings. This assessment is divided into the verification of:

- environmental impact of the materials used for the construction of the building
- water impact of the building
- indoor air quality
- protection from radon gas
- natural lighting
- acoustic comfort

Minimum prerequisites for CasaClima Nature certification are the following:

- envelope efficiency: CasaClima class A
- overall efficiency: CasaClima class A

Environmental impact of the materials used for the construction of the building

The limit value (maximum value) of the score for the impact of building materials (ICC) for the purposes of CasaClima Nature certification is 300 points for all buildings (residential and non-residential).

The ICC indicator or Nature score for evaluating the environmental impact of building materials is calculated with reference to the materials/products making up the opaque and transparent envelope by following the following guidelines:

Table 31: Evaluation system for the environmental impact

Structural elements	Consider the same dissipating constructive elements taken into consideration for the purposes of the CasaClima energy calculation.
Exclusions	For the purposes of CasaClima Nature certification, the following elements must not be included in the calculation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - structural elements of the unheated envelope - internal walls and floors - external or internal stairs of all types - punctual foundation structures (plinths, poles) - terraces, parapets, ledges (e.g. from the roof), balconies
Finishes, coatings, sheaths and sheets	Unlike for the energy calculation, all internal and external finishes and all coatings beyond the ventilation layer (walls and roofs) must be included in the calculation for the purposes of Nature certification. All the materials/products that make up the stratigraphy must also be included, even if they are not significant for the energy calculation (such as sheets, sheaths, etc.)

The evaluation of the impact of construction materials takes place through the quantitative calculation of the ICC indicator (or Nature score), based on an environmental impact balance in which the following parameters are assessed:

- Non-renewable primary energy input (PEI)
- Acidification potential (AP)
- Global warming potential (GWP100)
- Durability of materials (use time t_u)

If the product used has an environmental product declaration (EPD) according to ISO 14025 and EN 15804, it is possible to insert in the calculation program the values of the environmental parameters certified in the EPD.

In calculating the environmental impact of materials, bonus points can be attributed for regional materials/products and/or materials/products that have a third-party ecological certification and/or materials produced in a plant which obtained the KlimaFactory nameplate. To be eligible for bonus points, the materials/products used must meet the following requirements:

- Natural stone materials produced within 200 km distance from the construction site.
- Brick materials produced within 500 km of distance from the construction site.
- Wood materials with FSC/PEFC certificate or produced within 500 km distance from the construction site.
- Materials with third party ecological certificate (type 1 environmental label according to ISO 14024)
- Materials produced in a factory that has obtained the KlimaFactory label.

The use of the following materials is not allowed throughout the building (heated rooms, unheated rooms, including internal finishes and external arrangements):

- Products containing substances that contribute to the reduction of the ozone layer (e.g. chlorine-fluoro-carbides CFC, hydro-bromo-fluoro-carbides HBFC, hydro-chloro-fluoro-carbides HCFC, hydro-fluoro-carbides HFC). The substances are defined in groups I, II, III, IV, V, VI, VII, VIII, IX and "New Substances" annex I and II of Regulation (EC) N.1005/2009 and subsequent amendments.
- Plastics containing heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, chromium VI, mercury.
- Plastics containing organic tin compounds such as TBT, TPT, DBT.
- Plastics containing both high and low molecular weight phthalates.
- Lead sheets and sheets.
- Tropical wood without FSC or PEFC certification.

Water impact of the building

The water impact index defines the degree of improvement of the building compared to a standard building and returns a value that takes into account:

- efficiency of the installed hydraulic device.
- degree of waterproofing of the surfaces.
- possible presence of recovery systems and/o infiltration of rainwater.
- any systems for the reuse of gray water or on-site disposal of wastewater.

The minimum requirement for a Nature certification is a water impact index $W_{kw} \geq 30\%$.

The calculation of the water impact index, the following parameters are considered:

- type of flooring/roof and relative area.
- methods of outflow/infiltration of rainwater falling on the different areas.
- days of use of the building (350 days for residential), average number of people present and rainfall data of the location ($\text{mm}/\text{m}^2\text{a}$).
- heated net area and glazed area of the building.
- sizing data of any recovery, infiltration, disposal plants on site (rainwater, gray or waste water) in m^3/a .
- number of plumbing installations in the entire building and related type.

Indoor air quality

To verify the air quality inside buildings, at least one of the following criteria must be met:

- a) presence of controlled mechanical ventilation or
- b) use of materials and products indoors (including interior finishing materials: floors, coatings, paints etc.), which comply with the requirements described in the following.

For compliance with point a), in the case of residential buildings, the presence of both central and decentralized controlled mechanical ventilation systems is allowed. In both cases, project ventilation rates are required to ensure an air exchange of at least 0.4 vol/h in all housing units. (omissis)

With reference to point b) for the release of the CasaClima Nature certification it is necessary that the finishing works (laying floors, interior coverings, paintings etc.) are completed in all the residential units of the building.

If none of the above criteria are met, a final measurement of indoor air quality is required, to be paid by the applicant, according to the methods described below.

For compliance with the criterion, the following materials/products are checked:

- Materials and products based on glued wood as defined by Ministerial Decree 10.10.2008: raw or coated panels, plywood, beams, walls, floors.
- Materials for thermal and/or acoustic insulation for interiors.
- Liquid products applied on internal surfaces (excluding windows and doors) as defined by directive 2004/42/EC and by the decision 2014/312/UE): varnishes, paints, impregnating agents, lacquers, primers, etc.

Compliance with the requirements is required for all elements inside the heated volume (beams, load-bearing and non-load-bearing wood-based panels, cladding, floors, thermal and acoustic insulation) that have an emission surface placed inside the airtight layer (including the elements that make up the airtight layer).

Protection from radon gas

For new buildings, a preventive radon risk analysis is required based on:

- mapping of indoor radon
- geomorphological analysis of the site (signed by a geologist), in which any localized radon risk situations are identified. The geomorphological analysis of the site is not necessary if the mapping already identifies the area as a radon risk area (average annual concentration > 200 Bq/m³).

In the absence of geomorphological analysis of the site or in the absence of mapping, the adoption of the measures to protect against the risk of radon is always required. Information on radon risk areas can be requested from regional or provincial environmental agencies (ARPA or APPA).

For residential buildings with controlled mechanical ventilation, the requirement is automatically considered satisfied if the following additional criteria are met:

- the buildings are not located in areas classified according to the high-risk radon map (average annual concentration > 400 Bq/m³).
- mechanical ventilation controlled is installed in all housing units and complies with the requirements set out in point 4.1 of the CasaClima Nature directive.
- the inlet and outlet flow rates are balanced, or a slight overpressure is guaranteed inside the building.
- the external air intake is placed at least 80 cm above the ground level.
- heated rooms (even if not continuously) do not have vertical structures in direct contact with the ground.

Natural lighting

For the verification of natural lighting inside the rooms, at least one of the following requirements must be met:

- a) average daylight factor FLDm as per table N10. The verification of this requirement takes place through measurements/assessments on site by the CasaClima authorized auditor once the building is completed.
- b) aero-illuminating ratio of at least 1/5 in the environments referred to in table N10. The aero-illuminating ratio is calculated as the ratio between the glazed surface and the walkable surface of the entire environment.
- c) at least 70% of the vertical surfaces towards the outside that delimit the rooms referred to in table N10 must be glazed.

Acoustic comfort

The following table shows the sound insulation limits to be respected. They must be verified on site according to the sampling criteria specified in the CasaClima Nature directive.

Table 32: Sound insulation limits

			Residential buildings and touristic buildings	Offices, commercial and recreational buildings	Hospitals and nursing homes
			Kat. A, C	Kat. B, F, G	Kat. D
Evaluation index of the normalized sound insulation of the facade	$D_{2m,n,T,w}$		≥ 40 dB	≥ 42 dB	≥ 45 dB
Apparent sound insulation performance	of vertical and horizontal partitions between rooms of different units R'_w		≥ 50 dB ≥ 55 dB*	≥ 50 dB	≥ 55 dB
Impact sound level	between overlapping and/or adjoining rooms of different residential units L'_{nw}		≤ 58 dB	≤ 55 dB	≤ 58 dB
Sound level of installations	continuous operation L_{ic}		≤ 32 dB (A)	≤ 32 dB (A)	≤ 25 dB (A)
	discontinuous operation L_{id}		≤ 35 dB (A) ≤ 32 dB (A)*	≤ 35 dB (A)	≤ 35 dB (A)

3.1 Differences between Italian and Austrian standards

Table 33: Differences in Italian and Austrian standards on ecology and LCA

Austria	Italy

3.2 Quality standards in high-volume and high-rise timber constructions – Definition of minimum requirements in Italy and Austria

klimaaktiv assessment:

Standard for multi-storey timber construction: **klimaaktiv Gold**

Besides the main topic material and construction method also the location, energy supply, comfort and health represent important "side topics".

Summary:

The ecological assessment of building material constitutes a minor part with 150 out of 1000 possible points (section C) in the overall consideration „klimaaktiv“.

The maximum score in section C (building material and constructions) is easier to reach with timber constructions compared to conventional building systems.

Caution: Also in timber constructions it is important to waive all ecologically critical substance and apply climate-friendly materials (insulation material, ...).

Declared products in building databases as well as programs for ecological assessments support the planning of ecologically model projects. (www.baubook.at)

Eco-Index OI3:

An extension of the BIGWOOD Standards by the points ecology or rather LCA is recommended. One opportunity is the description in which particular section a chosen component structure is located (for example: number, color, ... A+, A, B, C, ...), which enables a certain comparability.

For **walls** with a **OI3 value of 70** would reach a very ecological standard. More details for ceilings and other components, or the entire building should be defined in a later step (building components – planning/design guide)